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biodiversitydigitaltwin

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Glossary of Terms

Item	Description
API	Application Programming Interface
ASF	African Swine Fever
AUC	Area Under the Curve
CI/CD	Continuous Integration / Continuous Delivery
CNN	Convolutional Neural Network
CORINE	Coordination of Information on the Environment
CWR	Crop Wild Relative
DAP	Data Access Protocol
DAR	Digital Asset Registry
DDDAS	Dynamic Data Driven Application Systems
DDI	Distributed Data Infrastructure
DEIMS-SDR	Dynamic Ecological Information Management System - Site and Dataset Registry

EASIN	European Alien Species Information Network
ECS	Entity Component System
EEA	European Environment Agency
EIDC	Environmental Information Data Centre
eLTER	Integrated European Long-Term Ecosystem, critical zone and socio-ecological Research
GAM	Generalised Additive Model
GBM	Generalised Boosted Regression Model
GLM	Generalised Linear Model
GRIP	Global Roads Inventory Project
GUI	Graphical User Interface
HMSC	Hierarchical Modelling of Species Communities
HTTP	Hypertext Transfer Protocol
IAS	Invasive Alien Species
IASDT	Invasive Alien Species Digital Twin
MaxEnt	Maximum Entropy
MSG	Model Server Grid
MIME	Multipurpose Internet Mail Extensions
OPeNDAP	Open-source Project for a Network Data Access Protocol
OToL	Open Tree of Life
PD	Phylogenetic Diversity
pDT	Prototype Digital Twin
PFT	Plant Functional Type
RF	Random Forest
RCP	Representative Concentration Pathway
SVM	Support Vector Machine
UC	Use Case

Keywords

Biodiversity, Digital Twin, Modelling, Simulation, Prediction, High-Performance Computing

Disclaimer

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Executive Summary

Digital twins have been well developed in engineering sciences but their full potential in other fields remains poorly understood. The Biodiversity Digital Twin project (BioDT) aims to test the potential of the Digital Twin concept in ecology, especially in conservation biology, where no operational Digital Twins yet exist. To explore the potential of digital twins in general, BioDT is based on a multitude of use cases (UCs) that differ in terms of their scope and complexity. Some of the UCs are based on long-term research programs that have developed relevant models and data, in which case the main challenge of the UC is to put together the already developed components as a digital twin. Other UCs are based on more novel ideas and do not yet have operational models or even well-defined data sources, and hence these need to be developed simultaneously while building the digital twin. The prototype digital twins corresponding to the different UCs (short: pDT) are implemented through reproducible and well-documented pipelines that describe the interplay between data, models, and users, as well as the continuously updating nature of each pDT. The envisaged pDTs are expected to vary in the number and phases of development cycles – a feature which we anticipated by the selection of UCs ranging in scope and complexity to guide and inspire further teams in the future that aim to develop pDTs for their specific topic in biodiversity research.

This report introduces the considered UCs and respective pDTs, and describes the current state of the developed pipelines separately for each pDT. For each pDT, a brief overview of the domain area is provided, followed by an overview of the pipeline's combined key components (data, models) and its scripts. These key components are then described in more detail, also in terms of FAIR principles. Conducted small-scale pilot studies of each developed pipeline per pDT are described further and envisaged users are outlined.

To find synergies among the pDTs, common data sources were identified in terms of shared input data on weather data, climate data, soil data, land cover/use data, and observation data. This overview is presented at the end of this report, on which basis pipeline scripts of retrieving and pre-processing of input data as well as post-processing of output data have been scanned in order to identify building blocks that can be generically used for several pDTs within BioDT, as well as by the wider digital twin community outside of BioDT. The report closes with a conclusion and identified future work.

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1. Overview of Use Cases and prototype Digital Twins

The seven use cases (UCs) cover a wide range of species, systems, and applications. This diversity reflects that biodiversity research and conservation has, by definition, to deal with multiple dimensions and complex ecological and social-ecological systems. The UCs differ in terms of their scope, complexity, and levels of scale, extent, granularity of processes (from agents to large scale processes) as well as context. Some of the UCs build on long-term research programs that have existing models and data, therefore the main challenge of these UCs is to consolidate the existing components as a digital twin. In contrast, other UCs are pioneering DT approaches for novel research themes and prior to the BioDT project commencing may not have had operational models or well-defined data sources, and hence these are being developed as 'from the ground up' as DTs.

The UCs are summarised here:

- Two UCs, *Grassland Biodiversity Dynamics*, and *Forest/Bird Biodiversity Dynamics*, focus on species-rich communities and how they respond to environmental change and management. The same response is studied in the UC *Ecosystem Services*, which is focusing on cultural services provided by biodiversity and how people use the associated resources.
- Two UCs are studying genetically detected biodiversity, *Crop Wild Relatives* and *DNA detected Biodiversity*. The former attempts, in the context of food security, to improve the genetic pool of domesticated crops by exploring genetic resources from crop wild relatives. The latter tries to improve the global cover of DNA-based biodiversity monitoring. DTs are developed to identify priority areas for sampling, in particular on cryptic or poorly studied habitats.
- The UC *Real time bird monitoring with citizen science data* tests the feasibility of involving a large number of citizens (>100,000) in close-to-real-time biodiversity monitoring.
- The UC *Invasive Species* aims at predicting the conditions and extent of the future spread of invasive alien plant species, which are of political concerns as alien species are a major threat to biodiversity and hence ecosystem function and services.
- The UC *Disease Outbreaks* seeks to improve the management of the spread of wildlife diseases. As an example, the spread of African swine fever is modelled, which is a threat to domestic livestock and therefore of major social, economic and political concern.
- The UC *Pollinators* focuses on honey bees, both because they provide the ecosystem service pollination and because they are exposed, like pollinators in general, to multiple stressors, in particular modern agricultural practices (monocultures, pesticide applications) and climate change.

The overall task of BioDT is to develop and deploy *prototype Digital Twins* (pDTs) for each UC. This requires close collaboration of researchers whose main expertise is in technical platforms, data and UCs, workflows and FAIR principles, simulation, modelling and data analysis, and the integration with research infrastructure. The pDTs corresponding to each UC are implemented through reproducible and well-documented pipelines that describe the interplay between data, models, and users, as well as the continuously updating nature of each pDT.

2. Description of pipeline and pilot study for each pDT

2.1 Species response to environmental change

2.1.1 Biodiversity dynamics

2.1.1.1 Grassland biodiversity dynamics

2.1.1.1.1 Background of pDT

With this UC we aim to investigate how different weather conditions (e.g. climate change scenarios), soil conditions and management regimes affect grassland biodiversity and productivity. Such knowledge is required for adequate local grassland management regimes under current and future environmental conditions, and for harmonised, complementary management at the regional and landscape scale. Both could foster production and biodiversity conservation in grasslands. Starting with a well-observed study site in Germany (cf. *Pilot study description and results* below), additional sites across Europe can also be added.

The BioDT prototype (Fig. 1; pDT led by UFZ) employs the individual-based **model for grasslands** called GRASSMIND [1–4]. For a given grassland plot (typically an area of several m²), GRASSMIND explicitly simulates the processes that let biodiversity dynamics emerge (at a resolution of one m²): individual plants can establish, grow and die. These processes are influenced by the plants' interaction and competition for light, space and other limited resources. Thereby, the individuals differ in their traits (as they belong to different plant functional types (PFTs)) and their state (i.e. size). The simulated processes are further affected by external drivers such as weather, soil conditions, mowing events or fertilisation. **Input data** on these drivers can be obtained from (heterogeneous) available sources, processed and provided to the model. The **model output** in terms of different patterns of grassland biodiversity dynamics will be **accessible to users**. The output also allows comparison to biodiversity **observation data**. This **validation** step may lead to recalibration of model parameters (changing the **model configurator**), and to model modifications and improvement to better reflect the grassland dynamics and underlying processes. When the pDT will be fully developed, users can not only explore and interpret model outputs but **interact with the digital twin**, e.g. by demanding new data, model modifications, or by taking part in multiobjective management optimisation. We explain the pDT components, data demands, the model GRASSMIND, and the current state of pipeline development in more detail below.

Figure 1 – The Grassland pDT and its current state of development in a nutshell

(Observation data footnotes: 1-Integrated European Long-Term Ecosystem, critical zone and socio-ecological Research, 2-Global Change Experimental Facility, UFZ, 3-Nutrient Network.)

2.1.1.1.2 Data

The input data required to run the model for a given grassland site and scenario comprise weather conditions, soil composition, and management regime. For model validation and recalibration, we further need observation data from grassland sites – ideally for several scenarios of environmental conditions and management, and for several time points. Input data and, if available, observation data get combined and processed to .txt files that serve the GRASSMIND format (cf. *Pipeline scripts* below). They include (for each single plot to be simulated):

- i) daily time series of weather data (date, precipitation, air temperature, solar radiation, astronomic day length, potential evapotranspiration),
- ii) management actions (date, mowing height for mowing days, fertiliser amount for fertilisation days),
- iii) soil characteristics (silt/clay/sand proportions; layer-specific relative water content, field capacity, permanent wilting point, mineral nitrogen, porosity, hydraulic conductivity),
- iv) all dates for which the model output needs to be written to result files,
- v) observations (date, biomass/mowing yield/vegetation cover/leaf area index; either separately for different species/PFTs or for the whole plant community).

The processed .txt files i)-iv) are used to run the GRASSMIND model, while .txt files v) are used to compare with simulation results.

Data for the pilot study (cf. *Pilot study description and results* below) were retrieved by individual queries from researchers who collected them and from publicly available sources. A tool to query (meta)data (combined from different sources, e.g. eLTER, Copernicus) for specific sites is under development. This tool might be used to select suitable sites based on data availability and to regularly (e.g. annually) stream data to the DT application (either as model input data, or for comparison biodiversity data to model output). Alternatively, we are developing pipeline scripts for processing data from multiple sites, e.g. from a query to all eLTER grassland sites. In the process of this query, we developed a detailed guideline¹ describing the required input and observation data and their respective file formats (incl. example files, templates,

¹ Guideline on how to provide data from a grassland site for simulations with the GRASSMIND model (Taubert F., Banitz T., Wohner C.). <https://zenodo.org/records/10125790>

minimum needs and optional additional data). Any required input data not available from site managers/data holders can be retrieved from publicly available sources (cf. *Pipeline scripts* below). For observations, at least some information on grassland community composition is the minimum demand.

Thus, data can come from heterogeneous sources (e.g. eLTER site-specific measurements, meteorological data providers [e.g. 5], soil maps [e.g. 6, 7], land cover and land use maps [e.g. 8, 9], other DTs, virtual scenario assumptions). Input data processing includes unit conversions (e.g. from solar radiation to photosynthetic photon flux density), and calculation of additional characteristics not directly available (e.g. daily potential evapotranspiration based on weather data, vertical soil layer characteristics based on soil type libraries²). Observation data at the species level need to be mapped to PFTs (grasses, small and tall herbs, legumes) using taxonomic and morphological trait information [e.g. 10].

2.1.1.1.3 Model

The GRASSMIND model simulates multiple characteristics of grassland plots at 1m² resolution, different organisational levels (individual plants, populations of PFTs, community) as time series (daily resolution). We focus on output characteristics related to biodiversity and productivity (e.g. biomass of different PFTs), and additional output for which observations are available during model calibration (e.g. vegetation cover or leaf area index). The model is programmed in C++. It runs on Windows and Linux systems.

GRASSMIND already runs on LUMI, allowing for parallelisation over hundreds of cores. The runtime of 160 instances of GRASSMIND (10 year simulation period, 1m² area) is 30 minutes on a local machine without parallelisation, 25 seconds on the Windows-based HPC system Model Server Grid (MSG) at the UFZ with parallelisation (56 cores), and 2 seconds on a single LUMI-C node (128 cores). Test runs on LUMI were used to assess the number of single stochastic replicate simulations required such that the mean outcome over all replicates becomes approximately invariant and, thus, can be reasonably considered as representative (e.g. during model calibration).

2.1.1.1.4 Pipeline scripts

The first steps of pipeline development included data preparation for the pilot study (cf. *Pilot study description and results* below), used as input for GRASSMIND simulations or as patterns for model recalibration and validation. Daily weather data, date-specific management information and date-specific observation data (biomass, yield, cover, leaf area index; 2-4 times per year) and time-invariant information on soil composition were obtained via email requests to scientists responsible for managing the pilot study site (in heterogeneous formats, mostly .xls files) or by manual downloads. The data were processed (using R or Matlab scripts) to prepare suitable .txt files as input for the GRASSMIND model. This meant considerable efforts in collecting, correcting and completing data from heterogeneous files. It included, for example, unit conversions, gap filling in weather data, detection and correction of errors and inconsistencies (e.g. in date formats, deviations between yield observation date and management calendar), mapping of grassland species to the PFTs (cf. *Data*), and exclusion of observations not belonging to any of these PFTs.

This pre-processing work is highly case-specific and poorly transferable for applying the pipeline to a different site. One alternative towards a more generic pipeline would be air temperature and precipitation data accessible via UFZ's System for automated Quality Control of time series data (API³). However, solar radiation is not measured at the pilot study site and was accessed from different nearby weather stations run by Germany's National Meteorological Service (DWD). These weather stations are up to 40 km away from the site and do not always provide continuous and consistent weather data.

² TRIANET Soil. <https://www.nibis.de/~trianet/soil/boden4.htm>

³ SaQC – System for Automated Quality Control. <https://rdm-software.pages.ufz.de/saqc/>
<https://www.biodt.eu/>

Therefore, we developed generic Python pipeline scripts to obtain all required weather data for any given location in Europe ($0.1^\circ \times 0.1^\circ$ spatial resolution) for desired time periods, at daily resolution. These scripts allow retrieving the weather data needed (air temperature, precipitation, solar radiation) from the Copernicus ERA5-Land dataset (API, [5]). They also allow obtaining day lengths, and calculating potential evapotranspiration based on additional weather data that can be retrieved (daily min. and max. air temperature, dewpoint temperature, wind speed, surface latent heat flux). Finally, the pipeline scripts allow creating all weather input .txt files in the format needed for GRASSMIND (cf. i-iv) in *Data*.

A pipeline script was developed for checking whether a given location in Europe (a candidate site for simulations) is classified as 'grassland' according to publicly available land cover maps [e.g. 8, 9; further maps will be included⁴]. For eLTER sites, a specific function was added to the Python package 'deims'⁵ for retrieving the spatial coordinates of sites based on their IDs in the DEIMS-SDR⁶.

Pipeline scripts are being developed for deriving applied grassland management regimes from publicly available land use intensity maps [11, 12]. These maps (at 20 or 30m grid resolution, available for Germany between 2017-2020) contain the frequency and average dates of grassland mowing events, and whether it was fertilized or not. To estimate the specific fertilisation regimes (amounts and dates), we use the German regulation on the application of fertilisers⁷ and a survey of common grassland management practices [13]. Additional remote sensing products on grassland management for other European countries will be added to the pipeline script when they become available⁸. If no management information is available, sites will be simulated with default scenarios of different management intensities (extensive/intermediate/intensive). The pipeline script for this default input data preparation is under development.

Pipeline scripts are also being developed for retrieving the soil composition (silt/clay/sand proportions) from publicly available soil maps [6, 7]. *Data*) either using composition-based soil type libraries⁹ and literature sources that map soil types to hydraulic properties [e.g. 14], or using pedotransfer functions [e.g. 15]. For the latter method, the required soil layer characteristics can also be retrieved directly from the global HiHydroSoil map of hydraulic properties [16] that is based on the SoilGrids250 map and pedotransfer functions. The pipeline script for this input data preparation step is under development.

For running the model on LUMI, scripts were set up for calculating the mean (and optionally other metrics like standard deviation) over a predefined number of GRASSMIND simulation runs such that storing all the output files of single runs is not necessary. Pipeline scripts have also been developed to transfer the computationally intensive recalibration of GRASSMIND to observational data (cf. *Pilot study description and results* below) from Matlab running on a local computer or the Windows HPC MSG at the UFZ to Python to be run on LUMI. This shall facilitate model recalibration through significantly faster computation time, better automatization and easier inclusion of additional observation data if they get available (cf. *Data*).

⁴ e.g. Grassland 2018 (raster 10 m), Europe, 3-yearly, 2020. EEA Geospatial Data Cat.

<https://sdi.eea.europa.eu/catalogue/copernicus/api/records/60639d5b-9164-4135-ae93-fb4132bb6d83>; ESA WorldCover 10 m 2021 v200. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7254220>

⁵ deims 4.0 (Bolton W., Wohner C.) Interface to the DEIMS-SDR API. <https://pypi.org/project/deims/>

⁶ Dynamic Ecological Information Management System - Site and dataset registry (the standard information management system for eLTER). <https://deims.org/>

⁷ Yearly nitrogen amounts allowed depending on mowing and environmental factors. Düngeverordnung - DüV, BGB, Germany. https://www.gesetze-im-internet.de/d_v_2017/BJNR130510017.html

⁸ e.g. LifeWatch ecotope map for Belgium. <https://maps.elie.ucl.ac.be/lifewatch/ecotopes.html>

⁹ e.g. TRIANET Soil. <https://www.nibis.de/~trianet/soil/boden4.htm>

<https://www.biodt.eu/>

The simulation results generated with GRASSMIND can be aggregated and visualised. To this end, we have developed Matlab scripts, which are so far specific to the pilot study. They can be adapted to suite data from additional sites, and serve as a basis for visualisations in the graphical user interface under development (cf. *Envisaged users* below).

If grassland observation data are available (cf. *Data*), observations below the total community level were usually obtained per species. However, the model GRASSMIND operates on the level of PFTs, i.e. groups of similar species (grasses, small and tall herbs, legumes, cf. *Model*). Therefore, a pipeline script for mapping species names to the PFTs is being developed, based on the Categorical Traits Dataset of the TRY database [10], which contains the required taxonomy and morphology information for more than 60000 plant species.

All generic pipeline scripts developed are shared in the BioDT GitHub repository (<https://github.com/BioDT>) and will be made publicly available (cf. *FAIR statement* below).

2.1.1.1.5 Pilot study

For the pilot study, we focus on one grassland site in Bad Lauchstädt, Germany (GCEF - Global Change Experimental Facility, run by UFZ [17]). This grassland site comprises of 20m² plots of grasslands, which are either extensively or intensively managed (mown twice or four times per year, respectively), and are kept under either ambient or expected future weather conditions (reduced precipitation mimicking expected climate change). Five replicates for each combination add up to 20 plots in total. For these grassland plots, the observations include measurements of aboveground biomass and vegetation cover (separate for various plant species and mapped to four different PFTs; cf. *Data, Pipeline scripts*), mowing yield and leaf area index (together for all plants on a plot). Measurements were obtained a few times per year throughout the period 2013-2022, varying with the different management regimes.

We are already work on improved model accuracy and predictive capacity by recalibrating and reprogramming the model to match the observations. Scripts for model calibration have been developed in Matlab. These run multiple replicate simulations for each of the plots and a given model parameterisation, calculate a goodness-of-fit measure based on the deviations between observations and model results (relative quadratic errors, unweighted means of all single observations for one plot, sum over all plots) and minimise this fit function using a gradient-free direct search algorithm (patternsearch [18, 19]). During minimisation, a set of PFT-specific GRASSMIND model parameters is allowed to be changed, while other parameters remain fixed to their default values. The selection of parameter values to be included, their constraints and initial values, the default values of parameters to be excluded, as well as specific settings of the search algorithm and the number of replicates needed for an adequate representation of stochastic model output are subject to thorough investigations. The minimisation procedure for calibration is parallelised and can be run on a local machine or the Windows HPC MSG. The current runtime for calibration on the MSG is in the range of one to several days, depending on the number of replicates and the parameters included. The transfer of the calibration routine from Matlab to Python and to be run on LUMI was started (cf. *Pipeline scripts*).

2.1.1.1.6 Envisaged users

We envision decision-makers (farmers, politicians) and scientists (grassland researchers, modelers) as pDT users. Beyond user access to the model outputs, summaries and further analyses of the model results, including comparison to observations, could be done and visualised. So far, such analyses are performed during model tests, exploration, calibration and development in semi-automatised and permanently evolving fashion. Selecting model analysis features for developing automatised provision to users is possible. We will further specify user demands during a workshop with potential users and data holders in late November 2023 (at UFZ, Leipzig, workshop together with the pDT on pollinator survival).

A graphical user interface is under development as an R Shiny application. This will facilitate user interaction by requesting specific scenarios to be simulated, analysed and the results visualised, or by communicating demands for specific outputs, new data or model improvements. Another option for user interaction that

may be implemented in the future is multiobjective management optimisation, where users communicate preferences for grassland dynamics to be achieved by management, management scenarios get optimised towards these preferences, and based on the results and insights on feasibility and tradeoffs of their preferences, users adjust those in an iterative cycle.

2.1.1.1.7 FAIR statement

Input data used from heterogeneous sources (cf. *Data*) will be referenced by persistent identifiers if published elsewhere. Otherwise, alternative documentation possibilities will be used, e.g. the eLTER Digital Asset Registry (DAR). The scripts and tools for obtaining and processing input data are shared on the BioDT GitHub repositories among pDT developers and invited test users, where they are further developed. They will be made publicly available in the course of the next project Task 6.2: 'Upscaling and implementing the DT'. The model source code is shared among model developers on a UFZ GitLab repository, and will be made publicly available. The data eventually provided to the model (model input data, biodiversity data for comparison to model output) as well as model output data generated will be made publicly available. While currently BioDT pDTs use the LUMI-O object storage and/or the LEXIS Distributed Data Infrastructure (DDI) for storing data, further solutions for public data access are being explored. Options for public data access also include repositories and open-access publications.

2.1.1.1.8 References

1. Taubert F, Frank K, Huth A (2012) A review of grassland models in the biofuel context. *Ecol Model* 245:84–93. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolmodel.2012.04.007>
2. Taubert F, Hetzer J, Schmid JS, Huth A (2020) The role of species traits for grassland productivity. *Ecosphere* 11:e03205. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ecs2.3205>
3. Hetzer J, Huth A, Taubert F (2021) The importance of plant trait variability in grasslands: a modelling study. *Ecol Model* 453:109606. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolmodel.2021.109606>
4. Schmid JS, Huth A, Taubert F (2022) Impact of mowing frequency and temperature on the production of temperate grasslands: explanations received by an individual-based model. *Oikos* 2022:e09108. <https://doi.org/10.1111/oik.09108>
5. Muñoz Sabater, J (2019) ERA5-Land hourly data from 1950 to present. Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S) Climate Data Store (CDS). <https://doi.org/10.24381/cds.e2161bac>
6. Hengl T, Jesus JM de, Heuvelink GBM, et al (2017) SoilGrids250m: Global gridded soil information based on machine learning. *PLOS ONE* 12:e0169748. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0169748>
7. Ließ M, Gebauer A, Don A (2021) Machine learning with GA optimization to model the agricultural soil-landscape of Germany: an approach involving soil functional types with their multivariate parameter distributions along the depth profile. *Front Environ Sci* 9. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fenvs.2021.692959>
8. Preidl S, Lange M, Doktor D (2020) Land cover classification map of Germany's agricultural area based on Sentinel-2A data from 2016. PANGAEA. <https://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.910837>
9. Pflugmacher D, Rabe A, Peters M, Hostert P (2018) Pan-European land cover map of 2015 based on Landsat and LUCAS data. PANGAEA. <https://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.896282>
10. Kattge J, Díaz S, Lavorel S, et al (2011) TRY – a global database of plant traits. Categorical traits dataset. *Glob Change Biol* 17:2905–2935. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2486.2011.02451.x>
11. Lange M, Feilhauer H, Kühn I, Doktor D (2022) Mapping land-use intensity of grasslands in Germany with machine learning and Sentinel-2 time series. *Remote Sens Environ* 277:112888. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rse.2022.112888>
12. Schwieder M, Wesemeyer M, Frantz D, et al (2022) Mapping grassland mowing events across Germany based on combined Sentinel-2 and Landsat 8 time series. *Remote Sens Environ* 269:112795. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rse.2021.112795>
13. Vogt J, Klaus V, Both S, et al (2019) Eleven years' data of grassland management in Germany. *Biodivers Data J* 7:e36387. <https://doi.org/10.3897/BDJ.7.e36387>
14. Rawls WJ, Ahuja LR, Brakensiek DL, Shirmohammadi A (1993) Infiltration and soil water movement. In: *Handbook of hydrology*. McGraw-Hill Inc., New York, NY

15. Tóth B, Weynants M, Nemes A, et al (2015) New generation of hydraulic pedotransfer functions for Europe. *Eur J Soil Sci* 66:226–238. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ejss.12192>
16. Simons, G, Koster R, Droogers P, 2020. HiHydroSoil v2.0 - A high resolution soil map of global hydraulic properties. FutureWater report 134, Wageningen, The Netherlands
17. Schädler M, Buscot F, Klotz S, et al (2019) Investigating the consequences of climate change under different land-use regimes: a novel experimental infrastructure. *Ecosphere* 10:e02635. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ecs2.2635>
18. The MathWorks Inc. (2021). Optimization Toolbox version: 9.2 (R2021b), Natick, Massachusetts: The MathWorks Inc. <https://www.mathworks.com>
19. Lewis RM, Shepherd A, Torczon V (2007) Implementing generating set search methods for linearly constrained minimization. *SIAM J Sci Comput* 29, 2507–2530. <https://doi.org/10.1137/050635432>

2.1.1.2 Forest/bird biodiversity dynamics

2.1.1.2.1 Background of pDT

This UC aims to investigate how different forest management strategies (treatment options) and climate change scenarios affect the forest and biodiversity. The ultimate aim is to find the most appropriate treatment option that improves biodiversity in terms of conservation or adaptivity for a specific forest stand under various climate scenarios. We will start with forests and bird species in Finland. Once we have the proof-of-concept study, we will consider other European countries and different species.

Virtual representations of Finnish forests are developed with the forest simulator called LANDIS-II [1] and biodiversity models are developed with Hierarchical Modelling of Species Communities (HMSC) [2, 3]. The forest digital twin consists of these two models. **Forest simulations** under different management options, together with climate change scenarios, predict possible future environmental conditions. **Biodiversity models** that relate species dynamics to environmental conditions predict how biodiversity responds to those scenarios. To demonstrate the benefits of having the forest digital twin, **decision support with interactive multiobjective optimisation** is used to find the most appropriate forest management option for the relevant forest stand, considering the ecological, social, and economic objectives, climate change scenarios, and the preferences of the stakeholders involved. The proposed digital twin application in a nutshell can be found in Figure 2, where the green components are ready to use.

Figure 2 – The Forest Biodiversity pDT in a nutshell

2.1.1.2.2 Data

Forest simulator

Forest data (source: Natural Resource Institute (LUKE)): Detailed information about current land use and forest structure over a continuous grid is openly available as multi-source national forest inventory data produced by LUKE.

Climate data (source: Earth System Grid Federation¹⁰): Climate data was downloaded through the Earth System Grid Federation with the ensemble r2i1p1. For the current time series, we averaged the monthly data from the last 30 years and projections of future monthly changes according to two different radiative forcing scenarios, known as Representative Concentration Pathways (RCP; e.g. [4]), namely RCP 4.5 and RCP 8.5.

Biodiversity models

Species occurrence data (source: Finnish Museum of Natural History (LUOMUS)): The species data covers the years 2007 to 2019 and includes in a total of 2920 transects for which the occurrences of 190 bird species were recorded.

Species trait data (source: [5]): various ecological traits (e.g., migratory status, body size, resource use) are available for the 190 bird species, as well as, e.g., their red-list status.

Environmental variable values (source: LANDIS-II outputs): The predicted volume of birch, pine, spruce, and other trees' biomass, and mean age of the trees are coming from LANDIS-II outputs.

2.1.1.2.3 Models

Forest simulator

LANDIS-II¹¹ is a landscape model designed to simulate forest succession and disturbances. It is openly available with extensive documentation on GitHub¹² and highly customisable, with dozens of extensions¹³ to choose from. Forest simulations have been conducted with LANDIS-II PnET-Succession extension V4.0.1 [6] for a combination of climatic scenarios (e.g., RCP 4.5 and RCP 8.5) and the following management strategies (e.g., no harvest, current clearcut rotation, clearcut with longer rotation length, clearcut with shorter rotation length and uneven-aged forestry). We run the LANDIS-II simulator for the entire Finnish forest on LUMI because this is a highly computationally demanding process. LANDIS-II outputs the predicted forest structure in the future under the given management option and climate scenario, and environmental values.

Biodiversity models

As the biodiversity model, we use HMSC [2, 3], which belongs to the class of joint species distribution models [7]. HMSC models species-environmental relationships using a generalised linear model and is able to borrow information among species based on their trait similarity and phylogenetic similarity. HMSC is currently implemented as an R-package [8] that is available in CRAN¹⁴ and GitHub¹⁵. Fitting HMSC models to large data sets and making spatially extensive predictions is computationally intensive. While the current version of HMSC is partially HPC-compatible, it does not utilise, e.g., GPU computation, compromising its scalability to large data. To overcome this bottleneck, we are currently translating HMSC into TensorFlow/Python, which we plan to run in LUMI. HMSC outputs the predicted bird distributions in the future under the given management option and climate scenario.

¹⁰ <https://esgf-node.llnl.gov/projects/esgf-llnl/>

¹¹ <https://www.landis-ii.org/home>

¹² <https://github.com/LANDIS-II-Foundation>

¹³ <https://www.landis-ii.org/extensions>

¹⁴ <https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/Hmsc/index.html>

¹⁵ <https://github.com/hmsc-r/HMSC>

Interactive multiobjective optimization method

Interactive methods have been found useful since they allow the decision maker to take part in the solution process iteratively and, at the same time, learn about the trade-offs and what kind of solutions are available [9, 10]. We use the open-source software framework DESDEO¹⁶ [11] for interactively solving multiobjective optimisation problems. It is developed in Python and freely available on GitHub¹⁷. We use some of the existing interactive multiobjective optimisation methods (we select one of them based on the stakeholders' preferred way of providing their preferences) and involve stakeholders iteratively in the decision-making process so that they can explore different treatment options under different scenarios and learn the feasibility of their preferences. The output of this process is the most appropriate (preferred) treatment option (i.e., most appropriate forest management strategy) for each considered forest stand based on the identified objectives and various climate scenarios.

2.1.1.2.4 Pipeline scripts

Configurator

Input: Decision variable values (i.e., management option for each forest stand and climate scenario).

Output: Text files necessary to run the forest simulator LANDIS-II.

Technical details: LANDIS-II necessitates text files including the management strategies and climate scenarios to be considered in the simulation. We implement a configurator in Python that converts the solutions recommended by the interactive method (i.e., a management strategy for each forest stand) under the given climate scenario to run the forest simulator LANDIS-II.

Converter (3-a in Figure 2)

Input: Predicted outcomes by LANDIS-II (the volume of birch, pine, spruce, and other trees' biomass and mean age of the trees)

Output: TIF files necessary to run HMSC models

Technical details: We implement a R script to convert the LANDIS-II outputs to the format that HMSC can use to predict the bird distributions.

Interpreter

Input: Predicted outcomes by LANDIS-II and biodiversity model

Output: Objective and constraint function values (i.e., social, economic, ecological)

Technical details: The LANDIS-II and biodiversity models generate different kinds of outputs as predictions. Interactive methods need the evaluation of objective and constraint functions considered in the multiobjective optimisation problem. Some functions may have analytical function formulation, but some other functions may need information generated by either LANDIS-II or the biodiversity model. We implement an interpreter in Python that uses the predicted outcomes to calculate each objective and constraint function value.

¹⁶ <https://desdeo.it.jyu.fi/>

¹⁷ <https://github.com/industrial-optimization-group/DESDEO>
<https://www.biodt.eu/>

2.1.1.2.5 Pilot study

For the pilot study, our initial focus is on Finnish forests and bird species. The study covers the entire country of Finland, which totals 33.8 million hectares, 77% of which is covered by forests.

The LANDIS-II [1] spatial explicit forest landscape model is utilised to predict future forest characteristics in the study area. The forest landscape is represented by an interconnected grid of cells. In this study, we set the cell resolution to 250 m (6.25 ha) and simulated forest dynamics at 10-year time steps. In the current study, we consider seven management regimes applied on the forest stands in the study area that is either being implemented or considered for application in Finland by government agencies: BAU (business as usual), SA (set aside – no management), EXT10 (BAU with postponed final harvesting by 10 years), EXT30 (BAU with postponed final harvesting by ≥ 30 years), GTR30 (BAU with 30 green trees retained/ha at final harvest), NTLR (No thinning – final harvest threshold values as in BAU), NTSR (No thinning – minimum final harvest threshold values).

We project future distributions of boreal forest birds in Finland, using a combination of LANDIS-II simulations and predictive species distribution models developed with Hierarchical Modelling of Species Communities (HMSC) [2, 3]. We predict bird distributions as a response to climate and forest management scenarios for the coming decades (until 2100).

In the pilot study, we modify usually considered objectives in managing forests and use the following objective functions:

- Maximise sustainable timber production: This objective aims to maximise the amount of timber that can be harvested from the forest stand while ensuring the long-term sustainability of the forest ecosystem.
- Maximise carbon storage: This objective aims to maximise the amount of carbon stored in the forest ecosystem, which helps mitigate climate change.
- Maximise deadwood volume: This objective aims to maximise the volume of deadwood in the forest ecosystem, which provides important habitats for many species and contributes to nutrient cycling.
- Maximising habitat suitability for specific species: This objective aims to maximise the number of bird species that can be found in the forest stand by promoting the growth and maintenance of tree species and structural features preferred by bird species.

The major bottleneck is the computation time of the models. Running LANDIS-II simulations and HMSC models for the whole study area in each optimisation cycle to evaluate objective functions is computationally intensive. This time-consuming process does not allow us to run models during the interactive solution process with the decision maker. Therefore, for the first pilot study, we decided to narrow down our study area to only one region, called 'Uusimaa'. Besides, we simulate all necessary management combinations (seven management regimes and three climate scenarios) and generate predictions to calculate objective functions, such as timber production, carbon storage, deadwood, and habitat suitability. Pre-computing optimal solutions before the actual decision-making process will allow us to save time and computational resources. Once this pilot study is managed, we then will generate results for the whole of Finland by running LANDIS-II in LUMI for all necessary management combinations. Moreover, translation of HMSC into TensorFlow/Python is in progress in collaboration with the ERC LIFEPLAN project. Based on current pilot work, GPU acceleration enabled by the TensorFlow/Python version is expected to reduce the overall model runtime by up to two orders of magnitude in comparison with the CPU-only R versions of HMSC.

Another important bottleneck of the pilot study is the objective functions coming from the corresponding literature [see, e.g., 14, 15] but not representing the actual objectives of current Finnish stakeholders and decision makers. We aim to identify important objectives for stakeholders who are either making decisions or are providing the necessary expertise for the decisions in forest management to find the most appropriate forest management strategy for Finland. To achieve this, we have identified key stakeholders and have started stakeholder interviews following the systematic way of structuring real-world multiobjective

optimisation problems [16]. The purpose of these interviews is to identify different perspectives and priorities regarding forest management and to better understand the challenges and opportunities associated with finding the most appropriate forest management strategy. After all the interviews, we will have a multiobjective optimisation model that considers the actual objectives of real stakeholders in Finland and conduct real decision-making processes by applying LANDIS-II and HMSC models for the newly structured optimisation model.

2.1.1.2.6 Envisaged users

The above-mentioned stakeholders are the potential users of the prototype DT. Once we conduct the qualitative analysis based on the interview data, we will have the better understanding of their objectives, decision options, and constraints, and will tailor the multiobjective optimisation model accordingly. Those stakeholders making actual decisions, e.g., government and ministry representatives and state-owned companies can use the digital twin enabled interactive multiobjective optimisation tool to explore and see the outcomes of their preferences. Besides, those who are providing the necessary expertise to the decision makers can study different scenarios with the help of the pDT.

2.1.1.2.7 FAIR statement

The sources of input data, the data preparation procedures and the model output data shall be documented, while the level of detail is under discussion.

Input data used from heterogeneous sources (cf. 0.2) will be referenced by persistent identifiers if published elsewhere. The scripts and tools for processing obtained input data will be documented and made publicly available. The above-mentioned scripts are not generic; rather, they are specifically implemented for this pDT and its models, e.g., LANDIS-II and HMSC. Currently, they are shared among the modelers and collaborators within this pDT. It is important to note that the parameterisation of the LANDIS-II model for the pilot study is still in progress and not yet finalised. Once this process is complete, we will share the source codes of both scripts and models publicly on the BioDT GitHub organisation. The data eventually provided to the model (model input data, cf. 0.2) as well as model output data generated will be made publicly available (cf. 2.1.1.1.7 for discussion on options to achieve this).

2.1.1.2.8 References

1. Scheller, R. M., Domingo, J. B., Sturtevant, B. R., Williams, J. S., Rudy, A., Gustafson, E. J., & Mladenoff, D. J. (2007). Design, development, and application of LANDIS-II, a spatial landscape simulation model with flexible temporal and spatial resolution. *Ecological Modelling*, 201(3-4), 409-419. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolmodel.2006.10.009>
2. Ovaskainen, O., Tikhonov, G., Norberg, A., Guillaume Blanchet, F., Duan, L., Dunson, D., ... & Abrego, N. (2017). How to make more out of community data? A conceptual framework and its implementation as models and software. *Ecology Letters*, 20(5), 561-576. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ele.12757>
3. Ovaskainen, O., & Abrego, N. (2020). Joint species distribution modelling: with applications in R. Cambridge University Press.
4. Van Vuuren, D. P., Edmonds, J., Kainuma, M., Riahi, K., Thomson, A., Hibbard, K., ... & Rose, S. K. (2011). The representative concentration pathways: An overview. *Climatic change*, 109, 5-31.
5. Storchová, L., & Hořák, D. (2018). Life-history characteristics of European birds. *Global Ecology and Biogeography*, 27(4), 400-406. <https://doi.org/10.1111/geb.12709>
6. De Bruijn, A., Gustafson, E. J., Sturtevant, B. R., Foster, J. R., Miranda, B. R., Lichti, N. I., & Jacobs, D. F. (2014). Toward more robust projections of forest landscape dynamics under novel environmental conditions: embedding PnET within LANDIS-II. *Ecological Modelling*, 287, 44-57. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolmodel.2014.05.004>
7. Warton, D. I., Blanchet, F. G., O'Hara, R. B., Ovaskainen, O., Taskinen, S., Walker, S. C., & Hui, F. K. (2015). So many variables: Joint modeling in community ecology. *Trends in Ecology & Evolution*, 30(12), 766-779. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tree.2015.09.007>

8. Tikhonov, G., Opedal, Ø. H., Abrego, N., Lehtikainen, A., de Jonge, M. M., Oksanen, J., & Ovaskainen, O. (2020). Joint species distribution modelling with the R-package HMSC. *Methods in Ecology and Evolution*, 11(3), 442-447. <https://doi.org/10.1111/2041-210X.13345>
9. Branke, J., Deb, K., Miettinen, K., & Slowiński, R. (2008). *Multiobjective optimization: Interactive and evolutionary approaches*. Springer Science & Business Media.
10. Miettinen, K., Ruiz, F., and Wierzbicki, A.P. (2008). Introduction to multiobjective optimization: Interactive approaches, In: Branke, J., Deb, K., Miettinen, K., Slowiński, R. (Eds.), *Multiobjective Optimization: Interactive and Evolutionary Approaches*, Springer. pp. 27–57.
11. Misitano, G., Saini, B. S., Afsar, B., Shavazipour, B., & Miettinen, K. (2021). DESDEO: The modular and open source framework for interactive multiobjective optimization. *IEEE Access*, 9, 148277-148295.
12. Venäläinen, A., Lehtonen, I., Laapas, M., Ruosteenoja, K., Tikkanen, O. P., Viiri, H., ... & Peltola, H. (2020). Climate change induces multiple risks to boreal forests and forestry in Finland: A literature review. *Global Change Biology*, 26(8), 4178-4196. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.15183>
13. Panagos, P., Van Liedekerke, M., Jones, A., & Montanarella, L. (2012). European Soil Data Centre: Response to European policy support and public data requirements. *Land Use Policy*, 29(2), 329-338. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landusepol.2011.07.003>
14. Triviño, M., Pohjanmies, T., Mazziotta, A., Juutinen, A., Podkopaev, D., Le Tortorec, E., & Mönkkönen, M. (2017). Optimizing management to enhance multifunctionality in a boreal forest landscape. *Journal of Applied Ecology*, 54(1), 61-70.
15. Blattert, C., Eyvindson, K., Hartikainen, M., Burgas, D., Potterf, M., Lukkarinen, J., ... & Mönkkönen, M. (2022). Sectoral policies cause incoherence in forest management and ecosystem service provisioning. *Forest Policy and Economics*, 136, 102689. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.forpol.2022.102689>
16. Afsar, B., Silvennoinen, J., & Miettinen, K. (2023). A Systematic Way of Structuring Real-World Multiobjective Optimization Problems. In *Evolutionary Multi-Criterion Optimization: 12th International Conference, EMO 2023, Leiden, The Netherlands, March 20–24, 2023, Proceedings* (pp. 593-605). Cham: Springer Nature Switzerland. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-27250-9_42

2.1.1.3 Real-time bird monitoring with citizen science data

2.1.1.3.1 Background of pDT

This UC aims to investigate if and how citizen science can be employed to real-time bird monitoring, in a way that produces robust data also for scientific analyses. The UC aims to develop a www-portal that shows data and predictions with minimal delay compared to the real-world system. A pilot study is being implemented within Finland and, if successful, the approach should transfer easily e.g. for the whole Europe. The focus of this UC is due to birds being of interest to people, with the number of bird enthusiasts also being very large. At the same time bird populations are showing rapid responses to environmental change. One highly conspicuous phenomenon is that of bird migration, in particular the arrival of migratory birds to Europe during spring. Due to climate change, these migratory events are rapidly shifting to earlier in the year. The data to be collected will help understand the trigger of spring migration, in particular the influence of weather conditions.

The proposed digital twin application in a nutshell can be found in Figure 3, where the green components are based on ready to use software, and yellow ones will be implemented.

Figure 3 – The Real-time Bird Monitoring pDT in a nutshell

Note that, during the time of writing, the mobile phone application has been successfully implemented (see Section 2.1.1.3.5 for details).

In what follows, we list the inputs, outputs, and technical details of each component of the real-time bird monitoring digital twin application.

2.1.1.3.2 Data

Bird Classification model (CNN)

Input: Audio files that contain bird vocalisations recorded by citizen scientists by the mobile phone application, as well as the associated metadata (most importantly, space-time coordinates).

2.1.1.3.3 Model

Bird Classification model (CNN)

Output: Predicted classifications of bird species in each audio file (species names and the classification probabilities) as well as the associated metadata.

Technical details: As the bird classification model, we use a convolutional neural network (CNN) [1]. For model input, we use 128×129 matrices, which correspond to spectrograms of 3 sec audio clips. These inputs are images, where each pixel value corresponds to the intensity of the certain frequency bin at a certain time point. The model has four convolutional layers and a classification head of two fully connected layers. Since any number of bird species can be present at the same time in a recording, the model solves a multilabel, multiclass classification problem. It uses sigmoid activations in the output layer, and rectified linear unit activations in the hidden layers. The model was trained using labeled data from four bird audio repositories (Xeno-canto¹⁸; Macaulay¹⁹; Bird Sound Global²⁰; [2]) and applying several kinds of data augmentations [1].

¹⁸ <https://xeno-canto.org/>

¹⁹ <https://www.macaulaylibrary.org/>

²⁰ <https://bsg.laji.fi/>

<https://www.biodt.eu/>

Bird distribution model (HMSC)

Input: Predicted bird classifications (from the CNN model), weather data (source: to be defined), long-term species occurrence data (source: Finnish Museum of Natural History (LUOMUS)), and environmental data (source: LUKE).

Output: Predicted bird distributions and bird vocalisation activities over Finland, for a selected time period (past, present or future) for each bird species present in the data.

Technical details: As the biodiversity model, we use HMSC [2], which belongs to the class of joint species distribution models [10]. HMSC models species-environmental relationships using a generalised linear model and is able to borrow information among species based on their trait similarity and phylogenetic similarity. HMSC is currently implemented as an R-package [3] that is available in CRAN²¹ and GitHub²². Fitting HMSC models to large data sets and making spatially extensive predictions is computationally intensive. While the current version of HMSC is partially HPC-compatible, it does not utilise e.g. GPU computation, compromising its scalability to large data. To overcome this bottleneck, we are currently translating HMSC into TensorFlow/Python, with plans to implement this version on LUMI.

2.1.1.3.4 Pipeline scripts

Observation board showing predicted past and present future maps of bird distributions and vocalization activities

Input: The outcome of 2.1.1.3.3: predicted bird distributions and bird vocalisation activities over Finland, for a selected time period (past, present or future) for each bird species present in the data.

Output: Visualisation of predictions at an interactive www-page.

Technical details: The www-page will be created, hosted and maintained by the Finnish Broadcasting Company YLE.

Interpreter

Input: The output of 2.1.1.3.3: predicted bird distributions and bird vocalisation activities over Finland, for a selected time period (past, present or future) for each bird species present in the data.

Output: Feedback and guidance for the user of where and when to record next.

Technical details: We will apply Bayesian adaptive design [6] techniques to ask what kind of new data would be most informative for each prediction task.

Mobile phone application for recording bird audio

Input: The output of 2.1.1.3.2 (bird classifications for the audio of the focal user) and 2.1.1.3.4 (feedback and guidance of where and when to record next).

Output: Feedback and guidance for the user of where and when to record next.

Output: Bird audio with metadata (where and when to record next).

Technical details: The mobile phone application for audio-based bird monitoring has been built on an existing mobile phone citizen science platform (Research for JYU Mobile). The application will use hyperautomation [7] to interact with citizen scientists anonymously to both guide data collection to locations and times suggested by output of 2.1.1.3.4, and to provide motivating feedback. The background processes will be built using Research Vasara, which is an open-source technology. Participation in research will start a user-specific process in Research Vasara. The hyperautomation process generates an anonymous and unique participation key and integrates the key into the user's Research for JYU Mobile.

²¹ <https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/Hmsc/index.html>

²² <https://github.com/hmsc-r/HMSC>

<https://www.biodt.eu/>

2.1.1.3.5 Pilot study

We developed the mobile phone application "Muuttolintujen kevät" (Spring of Migratory Birds) and launched together with the Finnish broadcasting company YLE a campaign (radio, news, social media) to attract Finnish citizens to use it. Screenshots illustrating functionalities of the application are shown in Figure 4.

"Muuttolintujen kevät" phone application

Figure 4 – The developed mobile phone application "Muuttolintujen kevät" (Spring of Migratory Birds)

The phone application can be found under the name "Muuttolintujen kevät" from the Apple and Android application shops, but is currently available for download only for Finland. During the summer 2023, the mobile phone application was downloaded and actively used by 160,000 users in Finland. They submitted 3 million recordings from which c.a. 5 million classifications reached at least the 90% probability threshold of correct species identification.

The system has otherwise worked well, but the backend has sometimes been a bottleneck for returning the classifications back to the user on time, especially when there is a high load in the system. Predictive modelling with HMSC has not been implemented yet, so there are no pilot results to report from that part of the pipeline.

2.1.1.3.6 Envisaged users

The users of the pDT are citizens interested in birds. Specific campaigns that relate to schools, cities, and national parks are under development, but they have not been implemented yet.

2.1.1.3.7 FAIR statement

The sources of input data, the data preparation procedures and the model output data shall be documented, while the level of detail is under discussion.

Input data used from heterogeneous sources (cf. 0) will be referenced by persistent identifiers if published elsewhere. The scripts and tools for processing obtained input data will be documented and made publicly available. The data eventually provided to the model as well as the model output data generated will be made publicly available (cf. 2.1.1.1.7 for discussion on options to achieve this).

2.1.1.3.8 References

1. Lauha, P., Somervuo, P., Lehtikoinen, P., Geres, L., Richter, T., Seibold, S. and Ovaskainen, O. 2022. Domain-specific neural networks improve automated bird sound recognition already with small amount

- of local data. *Methods in Ecology and Evolution* 13, 2799-2810. <https://doi.org/10.1111/2041-210X.14003>
2. Lehikoinen, P., Rannisto, M., Camargo, U., Aintila, A., Lauha, P., Piirainen, E., Somervuo, P. and Ovaskainen, O. Crowdsourcing training material for automated bird sound classification – a pilot study. *Submitted manuscript*.
 3. Ovaskainen, O., & Abrego, N. (2020). Joint species distribution modelling: with applications in R. Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/9781108591720>
 4. Tikhonov, G., Opedal, Ø. H., Abrego, N., Lehikoinen, A., de Jonge, M. M., Oksanen, J., & Ovaskainen, O. (2020). Joint species distribution modelling with the R-package HMSC. *Methods in Ecology and Evolution*, 11(3), 442-447. <https://doi.org/10.1111/2041-210X.13345>
 5. Warton, D. I., Blanchet, F. G., O'Hara, R. B., Ovaskainen, O., Taskinen, S., Walker, S. C., & Hui, F. K. (2015). So many variables: joint modeling in community ecology. *Trends in Ecology & Evolution*, 30(12), 766-779. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tree.2015.09.007>
 6. Leach, C. B., Williams, P. J., Eisaguirre, J. M., Womble, J. N., Bower, M. R. and Hooten, M. B. 2022. Recursive Bayesian computation facilitates adaptive optimal design in ecological studies. *Ecology* 103, e03573. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ecy.3573>
 7. Haleem, A., Javaid, M., Singh, R. P., Rab, S. and Suman R. 2021. Hyperautomation for the enhancement of automation in industries. *Sensors International* 2, 100124. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sintl.2021.100124>

2.1.2 Ecosystem services

2.1.2.1 Cultural ecosystem services

2.1.2.1.1 Background of pDT

This prototype digital twin focuses on developing a digital twin to support the use, planning and management of cultural ecosystem services. Cultural ecosystem services refer to non-material benefits people obtain from ecosystems, including recreation, tourism, intellectual development, spiritual enrichment, reflection, and aesthetic experiences. The digital twin will track changes in these services and how people use the associated resources. To quantify the cultural ecosystem services of the physical landscape, a recreation potential model will be used, while species distribution models will be employed to quantify the biotic component. The key research questions is: **can trade-offs between recreational use and impacts on biodiversity be minimized using a digital twin approach?**

The Cultural Ecosystem Services pDT is comprised of two fundamental model building blocks: a recreation potential model and a species distribution model (see Figure 5). The outputs of each building block are overlaid in a mapping interface to allow users to compare areas of high/low recreation potential against spatial biodiversity trends.

Figure 5 – The Cultural Ecosystem Services pDT in a nutshell

2.1.2.1.2 Data

The recreation potential component uses data describing land cover (UKCEH Landcover Map), natural features (geology (e.g. Geomorphology of the Cairngorm Mountains), vegetation (e.g. National Forest Inventory; National Vegetation Classification), hydrology (e.g. OS Open Rivers) and access features (e.g. OS Open Roads, proximity to roads/buildings). For constructing individual preference scores for model features, individual scores will be built from different user types. Currently scores are considered for two user types (hard versus soft recreationalist).

The biodiversity data for the species distribution model is sourced from two BioDT-linked research infrastructures: GBIF and eLTER. GBIF data is accessed on per-species basis via an API (using the `rgbif` R package) and a derived dataset DOI is produced for each species. We found >450 species with over 100 occurrence records within the target area. eLTER data for the Cairngorms National Park eLTER site is signposted via the eLTER DAR (Digital Asset Registry) and hosted by the EIDC (Environmental Information Data Centre). eLTER data includes structured ecological surveys and camera trap data.

The species distribution model uses environmental covariate data accessed via Google Earth Engine. The data layers used are as follows: bioclimatic variables from WorldClim BIO Variables V1, elevation from NASA SRTM Digital Elevation 30m, percentage tree cover from MOD44B.006 Terra Vegetation Continuous Fields Yearly Global 250m, NDVI from MOD13Q1.061 Terra Vegetation Indices 16-Day Global 250m, soil pH and soil carbon from OpenLandMap Soil pH and OpenLandMap Soil Organic Carbon Content, land cover from Dynamic World V1. Future work will look to access data from the IASDT architecture being developed in context of the invasive species pDT.

2.1.2.1.3 Model

The recreation potential model was ported to run in R using the raster R package for geospatial computations. This avoided the compatibility issues encountered with running a model prerequisite GRASS on LUMI.

The biodiversity component of the pDT is implemented as a species distribution model in R using the package `flexsdm`²³ (Figure 6). After loading data from GBIF and eLTER, we use environmental filtering to thin the occurrence data and use 4-fold random partitioning to evaluate the model fitting procedure. Pseudoabsences are generated within a set radius of presence-only occurrence data. Model types currently implemented were generalised linear model (GLM), gaussian process model and support vector machine (SVM), however this may be extended to further types such as integrated models. An ensemble model created using the weighted (by performance) mean across each model type. The ensemble model is used to predict across the rest of the target area to produce species distribution maps.

Figure 6 – Workflow for the biodiversity component of the Cultural Ecosystem Services pDT

2.1.2.1.4 Pipeline scripts

All pipeline scripts for the biodiversity and recreation potential components of the pDT are publicly available on GitHub²⁴. The GitHub repository for the pDT hosts Docker containers for reproducibly running the models for each component (see the 'packages' section within the repository). Each pDT component has a corresponding readme. The biodiversity models are contained within a R markdown file providing a human-readable report for each model run. The user interface is a Shiny module in the BioDT Shiny app²⁵. The outputs of both pDT components will be interacted with within the Shiny app.

2.1.2.1.5 Pilot study

In the pilot study, biodiversity models were run for a target 100 species, with 28 of these model runs failing due to a data processing error in the GBIF data loading script. Each successful model run for each species took between 5 and 20 minutes to complete, depending on the volume of data available for each species, with more data resulting in longer runtime. Examples of maps produced by the pilot study are shown in Figure 7.

²³ <https://sjevelazco.github.io/flexsdm/>

²⁴ <https://github.com/BioDT/uc-ces>

²⁵ <https://github.com/BioDT/biodt-shiny>

<https://www.biodt.eu/>

Figure 7 – Maps of species richness (of the 72 species used in the Cultural Ecosystem Services pilot study) and the areas where citizen scientists are encouraged to visit to validate model prediction

Species richness was calculated as the stacked (summed) probabilities of each species occurrence probability in each cell. 'Wildlife recording priority' was calculated as the probability of occurrence, downweighed by the distance to nearest record the averaged across all species, therefore highlighting areas where the model predicts the species is present, but there is no record of the species in that area. Therefore, more data is needed to validate the model.

Figure 8 – Model performance as calculated by AUC for each species in the Cultural Ecosystem Services pilot study

The grey points represent each of the 3 model types and the blue point represents the performance of the ensemble model.

We found that the model performance was variable, however the ensemble model (mean weighted) of all species achieved an AUC (area under curve, 0-1, larger value = better prediction) >0.7 (Figure 8). We found that generalised linear models performed worst of the model types, whereas the ensemble performed the best (Figure 9).

Figure 9 – The model performance, as measured by AUC, of different model types fitted as part of the ensemble species distribution modelling procedure

The model types were generalised linear model (glm), gaussian process model (gau), support vector machine (svm) and ensemble model (meanw).

The recreation potential model results are not new and therefore are described in [1]. The R implementation had a shorter runtime than the previous GRASS implementation.

2.1.2.1.6 Envisaged users

It is envisaged that the Cultural Ecosystem Services pDT will be used primarily by two user types:

1. Those who wanted to enjoy the area and potentially contribute to citizen science programs (walkers, cyclists)
2. People who want to make evidence-based management and research decisions (land managers, policy makers, researchers)

These user needs are being considered in the design of the Shiny app. Users will interact with the pDT via a web interface which will be developed as a module within the BioDT R Shiny app²⁶. Interfaces will be based on an interactive map displaying:

- Recreation potential map (based on selection for hard/soft recreation initially and then customised by the individual).
- Opportunity to experience biodiversity (combined biodiversity model outputs and probability of experiencing biodiversity model outputs).
- High priority areas for wildlife recording which indicate where more wildlife recording is required to improve the biodiversity models included in the pDT. This follows the same principles trialled in the DECIDE project [2].

2.1.2.1.7 FAIR statement

An RO-Crate is being developed to provide FAIR metadata for the model outputs and code. Input data used for the modelling will be referenced using persistent identifiers if possible. If input data has not been published elsewhere, e.g. coming directly from an eLTER site, it will be documented using the eLTER DAR. All

²⁶ <https://github.com/BioDT/biodt-shiny>
<https://www.biodt.eu/>

relevant components such as the methods used to collect such data or the methods applied to process it will be publicly available on GitHub with documentation and links. The documentation will include a readme and an ODMAP protocol [3] to provide human-readable metadata and context to the SDMs. If deemed feasible and practical, intermediate data products will be published in the eLTER DAR.

2.1.2.1.8 References

1. Dick, J., Andrews, C., Orenstein, D. E., Teff-Seker, Y., & Zulian, G. (2022). A mixed-methods approach to analyse recreational values and implications for management of protected areas: A case study of Cairngorms National Park, UK. *Ecosystem Services*, 56, 101460. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoser.2022.101460>
2. Pocock, M., August, T., Rolph, S., Mondain-Monval, T., Jarvis, S., Burkmar, R., Baird, K., Pateman, R., Dyke, A., Wright, E., McInerney, G., & Turkey, C. (n.d.). DECIDE tool. Retrieved January 20, 2023, from <https://decide.ceh.ac.uk>
3. Zurell, D., Franklin, J., König, C., Bouchet, P. J., Dormann, C. F., Elith, J., Fandos, G., Feng, X., Guillera-Arroita, G., Guisan, A., Lahoz-Monfort, J. J., Leitão, P. J., Park, D. S., Peterson, A. T., Rapacciuolo, G., Schmatz, D. R., Schröder, B., Serra-Diaz, J. M., Thuiller, W., ... Merow, C. (2020). A standard protocol for reporting species distribution models. *Ecography*, 43(9), 1261–1277. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ecog.04960>

2.2 Genetically detected biodiversity

2.2.1 Crop wild relatives and genetic resources for food security

2.2.1.1 Crop wild relatives and genetic resources for food security

2.2.1.1.1 Background of pDT

Population growth and global change are the two major factors that are challenging food security. The human population has increased from one to seven billion just over the past 200 years and is expected to reach 11 billion by the end of this century [1]. However, agricultural production is decreasing by 2% each decade due to global change (IPCC AR5 WGII, 2014). To meet the Sustainable Development Goal targets by 2030 and to bring about zero hunger, we need to boost our food grain production by about 70% and for this we need crops with higher yields, nutritional values, and an ability to resist diseases and adapt to changing environments.

Domesticated crops have been under human selection pressure for ages and their gene pool is limited by the domestication bottleneck. To improve their genetic pool, untapped genetic resources are found in crop wild relatives (CWR) and traditional cultivars or landraces. Thus, the main aim of the CWR pDT is to enable the search for CWR and traditional cultivars that can contribute to improving domesticated crops to enhance their nutritional values, resilience to diseases and changing environments.

For the time being, we focus on improving the nutritional quality of a climate smart crop, grasspea (*Lathyrus sativus* L.). We can later extend the method to other crops such as: 1) wheat - to improve resistance to fungal diseases; 2) *Ensete ventricosum* (a climate smart crop that is only domesticated in Ethiopia but feeds more than 20 million people), to improve resistance to fungal and viral diseases; 3) coffee, to enhance resilience to climate change and improve yield; and 4) teff, for example to minimise lodging and improve yield.

Grasspea is a nutrition rich legume known for resisting drought, extreme temperature and poor soil. Through symbiotic association with *Rhizobium* bacteria, it fixes nitrogen and thus can grow even on degraded lands. It uses residual moisture for growth and is usually cropped after the main cropping seasons. If other crops fail, the same farms can be covered by it and it is usually considered a lifesaver in developing tropical and subtropical countries. Nevertheless, it presents a fascinating paradox, i.e. it contains a neurotoxin that causes permanent paralysis of lower limbs in adults and brain damage in children, if consumed over longer period as a major diet. It is quite widely distributed and has about 180 wild relatives meaning huge genetic resources for its improvement.

<https://www.biodt.eu/>

The toxicity of grasspea is affected by different factors such water stress, soil zinc content, salinity and day length or number of light hours per day during the growing season. Toxicity increases with water and zinc deficiency and with number of day light hours and salinity [2-6]. This means the same genotype may present different levels of toxicity under different environmental conditions, complicating the matter. We hypothesise that 1) grasspea landraces and wild relatives growing in dry areas and in zinc deficient and acidic soils are most likely efficient in water, zinc and sodium uptake; and 2) through improving these efficacies of grasspea, it is possible to minimise production of the neurotoxin. Thus, the main aim of this work is to model the habitat suitability of grasspea wild relatives and identify genotypes with adaptation to these environmental factors to present potential alleles to improve grasspea as a crop. Habitat suitability of grasspea landraces and CWR will be modelled using MoDGPI (modelling the distributions of germplasm of interest) and geographic areas that harbor germplasm of interest will be mapped (see Figure 10 for details).

MoDGPI (Modelling the distributions of germplasm of interest)

- It uses multiple algorithms of species distribution models to produce habitat suitability of landraces and crop wild relatives
- Maps from high performing algorithms will be ensembled and classified into suitable and unsuitable classes
- Values of environmental variables that predict germplasm of interest will be extracted at each of the grid cells (pixels) that present suitable classes and pixel counts will be plotted as a response curve and threshold of values will be decided
- user interface enables users to make modifications to the threshold values and make decisions on which germplasm to test or to collect

Figure 10 – The Crop Wild Relatives pDT in a nutshell

2.2.1.1.2 Data

Modelling the distribution of germplasm of interest (MoDGPI)

Input: MoDGPI uses two types of data as input. I) Occurrence data in the form of CSV format as response variable from GBIF and potentially also from other sources such as ICARDA, Genesys and crop trusts. II) Environmental variables as such as climate (bioclimate data), soil and topographic data are used as response variables in raster format. Climate data can be obtained from the CHELSA dataset [7], soil data can be obtained from <https://soilgrids.org/> and topographic data can be generated from SRTM DEM. At each of the occurrence points values of environmental variables will be extracted and be made ready as input into MoDGPI.

2.2.1.1.3 Model

Modelling the distribution of germplasm of interest (MoDGPI)

Output: MoDGPI has three outputs: I) habitat suitability maps of each crop wild relatives and landraces; II) tolerances to environmental factors that are of importance to the traits of interest (toxicity levels for

grasspea) in the form of response curves, with cutoff thresholds; II) areas that potentially present genotypes of interest, in the form of maps.

Technical details:

MoDGPI uses different high performing species distribution modelling algorithms such as generalised additive modelling (GAM; [8]), random forest (RF), generalised boosted regression modelling (gbm; [9]), and maximum entropy modelling (MaxEnt; [10]) to produce habitat suitability maps of model targets. The algorithms in MoDGPI function by relating occurrence points to environmental variables to produce habitat suitability maps. Results from all algorithms will be evaluated against test data using area under the ROC curve (AUC) and True Skill Statistics (TSS). Maps from less performing models i.e. with $AUC < 0.7$ and/or $TSS < 0.4$ will be dropped and only maps from high performing algorithms and models settings will be kept.

Maps from high performing models will be combined through an ensemble approach and binary maps (maps with suitable and unsuitable classes) will be produced using the maximum sum sensitivity and specificity threshold. The suitable class of the binary maps will be overlaid with a soil zinc map, soil acidity map and rainfall data, and their range of tolerance to these environmental variables will be generated as response curves. Each of the grasspea crop wild relatives will be ranked based on their range of tolerances to these environmental factors. For model targets with high tolerance to these factors, geographic areas where plants presenting the desired genotypes are growing will be mapped and provided.

2.2.1.1.4 Pipeline scripts

Users interaction with the digital twin (end user interface)

Users of the products from the twin can be plant prebreeders, researchers, conservation scientists and academicians. Users will interact with the DT via a web interface (likely to be developed using the BioDT R Shiny app). The end users can further collect samples from mapped areas of interest and test the performances of the genotypes. This is useful to improve the cutoff threshold for the environmental ranges of interest which helps to relax or constrain the environmental space where the genotypes of interest are potentially found. This ultimately helps the twin to improve the maps and rankings of candidate wild relatives. Distribution models capture potential suitable areas and thus may help discovery of new populations. With improvements of online occurrence data, the validity of models can also improve over time improving the robustness of the models. The habitat suitability models also have applications in conservation. The user interface should also enable users to constrain or relax the tolerance thresholds and decide geographic areas from which the germplasm of interest can be obtained. It should also enable them to prioritise the germplasms to be tested based quality and/or access. The modelling tools will also be made available to users. The pipeline scripts developed for modelling purposes are hosted on the BioDT GitHub organisation (currently within a private repository) and will be made publicly available.

2.2.1.1.5 Pilot study

Grasspea has more than 180 Crop Wild Relatives, with 86 of them featuring substantial data. We have successfully obtained the necessary data for the models and have executed model runs for these specific species. Our current focus involves the ongoing mapping of grasspea wild relatives, particularly those exhibiting acidity tolerance, although the results are currently in the preliminary stage (Figure 11).

Figure 11 – The habitat suitability assessment for grasspea's (*Lathyrus hirsutus*) crop wild relative

The illustration is achieved by merging 24 binary maps depicting suitable and unsuitable classes (a). The legend bar indicates consensus among these maps in forecasting suitable pixels. Panel b presents the model performances and the cut-off threshold used to generate binary suitable/unsuitable maps. This serves as a representative example out of the 86 species we subjected to similar modeling processes.

Our current tasks include:

- Refining the obtained results.
- Establishing a ranking system for populations based on multiple criteria.
- Developing a user-friendly GUI to empower end users, particularly plant breeders, in making informed decisions.

This procedure is being consistently applied to other traits of interest, such as water stress tolerance and response to soil zinc content.

All models are run at a global scale. To accommodate locally confined species, we constrained pseudo-absence points within specific geographic areas. Currently, the entire process has been adapted for universal applicability across all crops and traits. Consequently, our script can autonomously retrieve data on crop wild relatives for any crop and pinpoint the locations of traits of interest for plant breeders. The script is hosted on a private repository in the BioDT GitHub organisation and will be released to the public as it continues to evolve.

Figure 12 – The occurrence data used to execute models for *Lathyrus hirsutus*

White points denote locations of presence, while black points indicate pseudoabsence points.

2.2.1.1.6 Envisaged users

The envisaged users include: 1) agricultural researchers, specifically plant pre-breeders; 2) academicians such as eco-physiologists; 3) conservation scientists; 4) policy makers and 5) the public at large. It is of interest to plant breeding companies and international organizations interested in conserving them as well as benefit from them. These include: 1) ECPGR European CWR expert group, Rome, Italy; 2) Plant Treaty (ITPGRFA), FAO, Rome, Italy; 3) University of Birmingham, School of Biosciences, Birmingham, UK; 4) BrAPI Breeding API; 5) CGIAR ICARDA, Rabat, Morocco & Lebanon; 6) CropTrust, Bonn, Germany; 7) Alliance of Bioversity International and CIAT, Rome, Italy; 8) Nordic Genetic Resources Center, Alnarp, Sweden and 9) Norwegian Genetic Resources Center, Ås, Norway.

2.2.1.1.7 FAIR statement

We aim to document the entire provenance chain from the input data to the processing steps used, and from modelling to the generated output. Occurrence data used for the modelling will be referenced using persistent identifiers, if possible. Climate, soil and topographic data will be referenced. All data used in the models will be publicly available and free to use and share (with appropriate credit). Outputs from the pDT and the modelling tools to produce the outputs will also be publicly available. While currently hosted in a private GitHub repository to enable further development prior to a public release, scripts will be released to the public as they continue to evolve.

2.2.1.1.8 References

1. Roser M., R. H., Ortiz-Ospina, E., Rodés-Guirao, L. 2013. World Population Growth.
2. Fikre, A., T. Negwo, Y. H. Kuo, F. Lambein, and S. Ahmed. 2011. Climatic, edaphic and altitudinal factors affecting yield and toxicity of *Lathyrus sativus* grown at five locations in Ethiopia. *Food and Chemical Toxicology* 49:623-630. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fct.2010.06.055>
3. Haque, R. M., Y. H. Kuo, F. Lambein, and M. Hussain. 2011. Effect of environmental factors on the biosynthesis of the neuro-excitatory amino acid beta-ODAP (beta-N-oxalyl-L-alpha,beta-diaminopropionic acid) in callus tissue of *Lathyrus sativus*. *Food and Chemical Toxicology* 49:583-588. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fct.2010.06.050>
4. Jiao, C. J., J. L. Jiang, L. M. Ke, W. Cheng, F. M. Li, Z. X. Li, and C. Y. Wang. 2011. Factors affecting β -ODAP content in *Lathyrus sativus* and their possible physiological mechanisms. *Food and Chemical Toxicology* 49:543-549. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fct.2010.04.050>
5. Sarker, A., A. Fikre, A. M. Abd El-Moneim, H. Nakkoul, and A. Singh. 2018. Reducing anti-nutritional factor and enhancing yield with advancing time of planting and zinc application in grasspea in Ethiopia. *Journal of the Science of Food and Agriculture* 98:27-32. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jsfa.8433>
6. Siddique, K. H. M., S. P. Loss, S. P. Herwig, and J. M. Wilson. 1996. Growth, yield and neurotoxin (ODAP) concentration of three *Lathyrus* species in Mediterranean-type environments of western Australia. *Australian Journal of Experimental Agriculture* 36:209-218. <https://doi.org/10.1071/EA9960209>

7. Karger, D. N., A. M. Wilson, C. Mahony, N. E. Zimmermann, and W. Jetz. 2021. Global daily 1 km land surface precipitation based on cloud cover-informed downscaling. *Scientific Data* 8:307. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-021-01084-6>
8. Wood, S. N. 2011. Fast stable restricted maximum likelihood and marginal likelihood estimation of semiparametric generalized linear models. *Journal of the Royal Statistical Society: Series B (Statistical Methodology)* 73:3-36. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-9868.2010.00749.x>
9. Greenwell, B., Boehmke, B., Cunningham, J. 2022. Generalized Boosted Regression Models.
10. Phillips, S. J., R. P. Anderson, and R. E. Schapire. 2006. Maximum entropy modeling of species geographic distributions. *Ecological Modelling* 190:231-259. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolmodel.2005.03.026>

2.2.2 DNA detected biodiversity, poorly known habitats

2.2.2.1 Genetically detected biodiversity in cryptic habitats – prioritisation of sampling effort

2.2.2.1.1 Background of pDT

DNA-based methods are highly efficient in targeting organism groups that normally receive little attention, e.g. fungi, bacteria, archaea, protists, nematodes and micro-invertebrates. Methods are simple and cost-effective, also at scales where traditional sampling regimes would be too costly in terms of money, time and labour. However, to be able to include such data in global biodiversity conservation efforts, it is necessary to get at wider global sampling, and understand diversity in cryptic environments better. The case-study will focus on how a digital twin can be used to identify priority areas for further sampling, based on some user-defined criteria/constraints (i.e. one further sample in an overly rich and heterogeneous habitat type, may be more valuable than a sample from a sparsely sampled but very homogeneous habitat type).

2.2.2.1.2 Data

The DT will focus on Denmark and use eDNA metabarcoding datasets for fungi (and bacteria) produced under the Biowide project [1], as well as national maps of land-use types [2].

The first test data covers 130 sampling sites in Denmark, and the data is publicly available in many versions, one version is the Biowide Fungi eDNA DarwinCore dataset in GBIF²⁷. Our intention is to develop a model around eDNA data in the shape of OTU tables (species by site matrices). This is the native format for interoperable eDNA data, and the first data will be manually shaped (already is) in this format. This means that later versions of the prototype will need to be able to produce this tabular data from Darwin Core data, when we wish to pull data from the live GBIF.org database²⁸.

There is a vision to share data sources across pDTs for land cover / land use data used in the model. For the first implementation we will likely use a relatively fine-grained map for Denmark. When scaling up to global data aggregated in larger spatial bins, we believe the pDT can use global and coarser land use/cover sources.

²⁷ <https://www.gbif.org/dataset/3b8c5ed8-b6c2-4264-ac52-a9d772d69e9f>

²⁸ GBIF API description. <https://www.gbif.org/developer/summary>
<https://www.biодt.eu/>

Figure 13 – The eDNA sampling prioritisation pDT in a nutshell

2.2.2.1.3 Model

The pDT will allow the user to set basic constraints for future samples, and then use existing data to predict where further samples are best placed. Information from new samples will eventually feed into the model and provide an updated map of priority areas.

The model will identify priority areas for further sampling, based on some user-defined criteria/constraints (i.e. one further sample in an overly rich and heterogeneous habitat type, may be more valuable than a sample from a sparsely sampled but very homogeneous habitat type):

- Geographical constraints (countries, user defined larger areas)
- Landscape constraints (e.g. habitat type / land use class / ecoregion constraints)
- Taxonomic constraints (bacteria, fungi, protozoa, eukaryotes)
- Prioritization parameters (e.g. heterogeneity of communities within units)
- Number of samples

The first version will use pre-formatted OTU tables (sequence/species by sample matrices with sequence read abundances) as input for the model, to calculate community compositional metrics (for samples or spatial bins), used for later ranking/prioritising.

Later versions will use occurrence data from GBIF filtered to include only relevant data from selected genetic markers and filtered by one or several method-based, geographical and taxonomic categories (eDNA metabarcoding fungi and/or bacteria in the prototype), and binned at some selected spatial unit size – e.g. using Uber’s H3 system²⁹ (hexagonal hierarchical spatial index). The binned data will then be reshaped into OTU table like data that can be analysed with classical community ecological tools (e.g. distance metrics, and extrapolated richness measures, etc).

Each spatial bin (or sample/site) can/will also be assigned to any category based on the land use/landcover information used in the model.

²⁹ H3: Uber’s Hexagonal Hierarchical Spatial Index. <https://www.uber.com/en-SE/blog/h3/>
<https://www.biodt.eu/>

Selected metrics will then be calculated per bin/sample (hexagon): e.g. absolute and/or extrapolated richness, coverage, and various beta diversity metrics: community dissimilarity measures between all bins. If grouping by land use category, metrics will also be calculated per category: coverage, average community dissimilarity (beta dispersion). Other measures may be relevant to include – e.g. the uniqueness score [3].

For each spatial bins / sample a ranking/prioritisation score will be assigned based on the calculated metrics in combination with the user defined constraints (geography, land use of interest) and weighing of criteria/metrics (physical distance, coverage, beta/alpha diversity).

The basic concept for the user interface of this pDT would be an interface where the user can select taxonomic group / marker gene(s) of interest, and overall geographical constraints, as well as the type of spatial categorisation they wish to use (e.g. land use / cover), as well as the scale of spatial binning (e.g. 1 sq km). Then the relevant data is downloaded through GBIF APIs and from relevant sources of land cover/use, and the spatial binning and calculation of matrices and ranking are carried out. We then envision that the user is allowed to interactively select/deselect prioritisation criteria, and modify weights. It will also be possible to deselect hexagons (exclude them from prioritisation) to refine search and make it relevant. Some selections will require recalculation of metrics and scores. The visualisation should be an interactive (zoomable, etc.) map with spatial bins (hexagons) coloured according to weighted priority score, and a panel with overall statistics. The aim is to provide the user with the best locations for optimising global/regional/regional knowledge (gap identification) for biodiversity sampling given some constraints in study design.

2.2.2.1.4 Pipeline scripts

No scripts have been developed yet.

2.2.2.1.5 Pilot study

The pilot data has been mentioned above. It is a dataset from 130 (or more is possible) sites across Denmark. The pilot wold project would be to see if these 130 sites and a finely grained map with few land use/type classes, can predict/prioritise sampling localities to maximise potential complementarity of samples.

2.2.2.1.6 Envisaged users

The envisaged users include:

- Diverse projects targeting cryptic biodiversity with eDNA metabarcoding methods
- Researchers, in particular larger and smaller research projects targeting cryptic organisms with eDNA metabarcoding, and wanting to use estimated complementarity of future samples as the main or secondary criterium for selecting sampling locations/sites.
- Monitoring initiatives, with the option to specify localities/areas for further sampling according to selected criteria.
- Commercial companies, e.g. offering a biodiversity monitoring system financed by the novel development of digital tokens linked to monitoring biodiversity with environmental DNA samples (e.g. SimplexDNA's ³⁰ Franklins ³¹)

2.2.2.1.7 FAIR statement

We aim to document the entire provenance chain from the input data to the processing steps used, and from modelling to the generated output. Occurrence data used for the modelling will be FAIR in the sense that it is all openly available in GBIF.org, but the exact dataset used will also be defined by a persistent identifier for full reproducibility. Topographic data and other data will be referenced by persistent identifiers. All data used

³⁰ www.simplexdna.com

³¹ www.footprintcoalition.com/post/can-crypto-help-mitigate-the-mass-extinction-crisis-simplexdna-wants-to-find-out

<https://www.biодt.eu/>

in the models will be availed publicly and free to use and share (with appropriate credit). Outputs from the pDT and the modelling tools to produce the outputs will also be publicly available.

2.2.2.1.8 References

1. Brunbjerg, A. K., Bruun, H. H., Brøndum, L., Classen, A. T., Dalby, L., Fog, K., ... & Ejrnæs, R. (2019). A systematic survey of regional multi-taxon biodiversity: evaluating strategies and coverage. *BMC Ecology*, 19(1), 1-15. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12898-019-0260-x>
2. Levin, G. 2022. Basemap04. Documentation of the data and method for the elaboration of a land use and land cover map for Denmark. Aarhus University, DCE – Danish Centre for Environment and Energy, 77 pp. Technical Report No. 252 (map data downloadable here: <https://envs.au.dk/en/research-areas/society-environment-and-resources/land-use-and-gis/basemap/basemap04-geotiff-for-download>)
3. Ejrnæs, R., Frøslev, T. G., Høye, T. T., Kjølner, R., Oddershede, A., Brunbjerg, A. K., ... & Bruun, H. H. (2018). Uniquity: a general metric for biotic uniqueness of sites. *Biological Conservation*, 225, 98-105. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2018.06.034>

2.2.2.2 DNA detected biodiversity, poorly known habitats - phylogenetic diversity

2.2.2.2.1 Background of pDT

"Phylogenetic diversity (PD) measures the evolutionary history captured by a set of species and therefore describes a fundamental aspect of biodiversity. As recognised by the Intergovernmental Science Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services, the planet's evolutionary heritage is a form of biodiversity that ensures options for future generations. The tree of life is a storehouse of potential benefits for humanity and by conserving PD, we conserve feature diversity (broadly, the full range of different evolutionary features of a set of species) and future options for humanity." (IUCN SSC Phylogenetic Diversity Task Force, pdf.org).

Biodiversity is most commonly measured in taxonomic richness. For example, it is common to describe how diverse a genus or a geographic area is by counting the number of species within them. Phylogenetic diversity, a measurement of the branch lengths in a phylogenetic tree, is an alternative measure of biodiversity that provides a comparable, evolutionary measure of biodiversity not possible with species counts.

Phylogenetic diversity is an indicator that is pointed out in the recent COP 15 Global Biodiversity Framework to measure biodiversity. GBIF has a demo pipeline that generates PD metrics from GBIF data and OTOL (Open Tree of Life) phylogeny simply by choosing a geographic area and taxon/clade. The pipeline can be used to explore PD across different geographic and/or taxonomic groups in relation to policy making, prioritisation of conservation efforts, etc. However, even relatively simple searches (e.g. Felidae (cats) in South Africa) usually take several hours of computation, and the tool cannot presently be used easily as an interactive explorative visualisation tool.

With a significant improvement of computation time, the pipeline may represent a valuable tool for visualising/testing ideas of conservation effort, or simply to explore PD. In combination with further information (e.g. stratified shape files) the tool may be extended and applied in a digital twinning context to address hypotheses/questions such as: "Would specific areas appointed as nature reserves based on e.g. species richness also support high PD?".

2.2.2.2.2 Data

The model uses occurrence data from GBIF.org, either pulled directly from the APIs of GBIF.org³² or from the monthly snapshots of the full GBIF occurrence data³³. The Phylogenetic Diversity indices are calculated based on phylogenetic information from Open Tree of Life³⁴ or user provided phylogenies.

2.2.2.2.3 Model

The starting point is a fully functional pipeline (PhyloNext; Figure 14), which is fully documented on GitHub³⁵. The current pipeline brings together two critical research data infrastructures, GBIF³⁶ and Open Tree of Life (OToL) [3], to make them more accessible to non-experts. The pipeline is built using Nextflow³⁷, a workflow tool to run tasks across multiple compute infrastructures in a very portable manner. It uses Docker³⁸ containers, making installation trivial and results highly reproducible. The Nextflow DSL2³⁹ implementation of this pipeline uses one container per process which makes it much easier to maintain and update software dependencies. The pipeline is also compatible with cloud environments (e.g. Microsoft Azure Cloud Computing Services, Amazon AWS Web Services, and Google Cloud Computing Services). The PhyloNext pipeline builds on the software Biodiverse⁴⁰ [1] for calculating the metrics. GBIF Secretariat has developed a graphical user interface that may be used for further pDT developments in the BioDT project.

Figure 14 – PhyloNext – the core pipeline of the Phylogenetic Diversity pDT

2.2.2.2.4 Pipeline scripts

Fully documented in the PhyloNext GitHub repository (see above).

³² <https://www.gbif.org/developer/summary>

³³ <https://www.gbif.org/occurrence-snapshots>

³⁴ <https://tree.opentreeoflife.org/>

³⁵ <https://github.com/vmikk/PhyloNext>

³⁶ <https://www.gbif.org/>

³⁷ <https://www.nextflow.io/>

³⁸ <https://www.docker.com/>

³⁹ <https://www.nextflow.io/docs/latest/dsl1.html>

⁴⁰ <https://shawnlaffan.github.io/biodiverse/>

<https://www.biodt.eu/>

2.2.2.2.5 Pilot study

The PhyloNext pipeline has been installed and run on LUMI. The next steps in relation to the pipeline focus on establishing relevant benchmark tests to see if speed can / has been improved, to define some relevant research questions for pilot testing, and identify data adequate to address these questions. The pDT concept is also open to further extensions, e.g. via exploring opportunities to link the PhyloNext pipeline to predictive modelling methods.

2.2.2.2.6 Envisaged users

Depending on the taxonomic scope and geographic scope modelled, the pDT may be used for research (see e.g. [2]), students, and any other parties interested in visualising biodiversity measures at any geographical scale.

2.2.2.2.7 FAIR statement

The model/pipeline uses freely accessible occurrence data from GBIF and phylogenetic trees from OTOL. The code is freely accessible from GitHub.

2.2.2.2.8 References

1. Laffan SW, Lubarsky E, Rosauer DF (2010) Biodiverse, a tool for the spatial analysis of biological and related diversity. *Ecography*, 33: 643-647. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1600-0587.2010.06237.x>
2. Mishler BD, Knerr N, González-Orozco CE, Thornhill AH, Laffan SW, Miller JT (2014) Phylogenetic measures of biodiversity and neo- and paleo-endemism in Australian Acacia. *Nature Communications*, 5(1), 4473. <https://doi.org/10.1038/ncomms5473>
3. Hinchliff CE, Smith SA, Allman JF, Burleigh JG, Chaudhary R, Coghill LM, Crandall KA, Deng J, Drew BT, Gazis R, Gude K, Hibbett DS, Katz LA, Laughinghouse HD, McTavish EJ, Midford PE, Owen CL, Ree RH, Rees JA, Cranston KA (2015) Synthesis of phylogeny and taxonomy into a comprehensive tree of life. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 112(41), 12764–12769. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1423041112>

2.3 Dynamics and threats from and for species of policy concern

2.3.1 Invasive species

2.3.1.1 Invasive Alien Plant Species Dynamics

2.3.1.1.1 Background of pDT

The Invasive Alien Species (IAS) pDT (hereafter IASDT) aims to use statistical models to predict the conditions and extent of the future spread of invasive alien plant species. More precisely, IASDT contributes to the understanding of how the level of plant invasion (i.e., the number of IAS) changes across Europe, which IAS may pose the biggest threat to biodiversity and ecosystem service provisioning in the future, and what habitats are most susceptible to plant invasions and may require increased attention from managers. To this end, we model multiple IAS simultaneously in a joint species distribution modelling (JSDMs) framework, a technique that accounts for species co-occurrence patterns.

The architecture of IASDT is outlined in Figure 15.

Figure 15 – IASDT architecture overview showing the main components of the IASDT

2.3.1.1.2 Data

Data streams for the IASDT input data highlighted above will be prepared per individual data source (i.e., research infrastructure) and data type (i.e., species occurrences, habitat types, environmental predictors, etc.).

In the following, we describe selected layers in the data streams shown in Figure 15.

- **Dynamic Data Driven Application Systems (DDDAS) based workflows:** DDDAS⁴¹ is a conceptual framework that synergistically combines models and data to facilitate the analysis and prediction of physical phenomena [1]. It is a two-layer system design where data assimilation and feedback loops create a bi-directional information flow [2]. These workflows will prepare data from the data sources in processing steps and will output the data into HDF5/netCDF4 files. Subsequent changes in data sources will be detected through feedback loops, and new data will be assimilated into the output files. The workflows will also track the system's state as it changes from one workflow run to the next.
- **Data Grids (HDF5, netCDF4, and other file types):** The output files of the DDDAS workflows will be datasets that hold the "state" of the physical systems represented by the IASDT and will be structured as Grids [3]. A Grid is a data structure from the Data Access Protocol Data Model, represented as an association of an N-dimensional array with N named vectors (one-dimensional arrays), each of which has the same number of elements as the corresponding dimension of the array. Every array in the Grid will be associated with a geolocation (i.e., longitude and latitude) and represent a variable (e.g., temperature, taxon, or precipitation). The arrays in the Grids will be indexed based on the timestamp of when the data was recorded to add a temporal dimension to the Grid datasets. Data Grids will be fully described using metadata adhering to common standards for each data type.

⁴¹ <http://1dddas.org>

- **OPeNDAP Server:** Naturally, the data grids representing the state of the physical systems will need to be accessible by the JSDMs run at the LUMI (i.e., the IASDT). This will be done with a cloud-based solution based on NASA's Open-source Project for a Network Data Access Protocol (OPeNDAP⁴²) [4]. The OPeNDAP architecture uses a client/server model, with a client that sends requests for data to a server through a network, and the server answers with the requested data. Data can be easily accessed and queried from OPeNDAP using various programming environments (e.g., R, Python, JavaScript, Rust, C++, etc.). The OPeNDAP server will also store and serve the IASDT outputs for third-party access. The IASDT outputs will be the state of the pDT. Therefore, the state of the physical and digital systems will be available through the OPeNDAP server.

Data types and sources

- **Reference grid:** We will use the European Environment Agency's (EEA) reference grid⁴³ (Lambert Azimuthal Equal Area projection; EPSG:3035⁴⁴). The EEA grid is available at 1, 10, and 100 km resolutions⁴⁵. We decided to use the 10 km grid in our analysis. Still, it is possible to upscale or downscale the resolution in future versions of the IASDT when necessary, depending on the success and processing time of the models. All data listed below will be processed into this reference grid.
- **Model response variable (gridded distribution of IAS):** We obtained the most recent checklist of naturalised alien plant species of non-European origin for Europe from our collaborators at FloraVeg.EU⁴⁶. We standardised this list against the GBIF taxonomic backbone using the `rgbif` R package⁴⁷ [5], which resulted in an initial list of 1,447 species. Species-specific habitat affinity for most species was obtained from our SynHab⁴⁸ collaborators; we still need to assign habitat affinity using other sources for other species.

We collated presence-only observations from three primary sources (listed below; see Figure 16). Further data sources we do not currently have access to (e.g., DiSSCo⁴⁹) can be easily integrated into the workflow in future IASDT versions. We projected the merged species occurrence dataset into our reference grid and prepared species-specific gridded occurrence data. Species with too few occurrences will be discarded from analyses.

- *Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF):* We used the `rgbif` R package to download the most up-to-date version of occurrence data for each species (a total of >10 million occurrences, March 2023). Doubtful occurrences and occurrences with high spatial uncertainty were excluded.
- *European Alien Species Information Network (EASIN)⁵⁰:* EASIN (European Commission - Joint Research Centre) provides spatial data on 14,321 alien species. EASIN data is available as presence-only grids at the same projection of our current reference grid (10-km resolution). Our workflow standardises EASIN's taxa names against the GBIF taxonomic backbone and extracts data on species of interest using EASIN's API. Thirty-two partners shared their data with EASIN

⁴² <https://www.opendap.org>

⁴³ <https://www.eea.europa.eu/en/datahub/datahubitem-view/3c362237-daa4-45e2-8c16-aaadfb1a003b>

⁴⁴ <https://epsg.io/3035>

⁴⁵ <https://www.eea.europa.eu/data-and-maps/figures/eea-reference-grids>

⁴⁶ <https://floraveg.eu/>

⁴⁷ <https://github.com/ropensci/rgbif>

⁴⁸ <https://www.synhab.com/>

⁴⁹ <https://www.dissco.eu/>

⁵⁰ <https://easin.jrc.ec.europa.eu/easin>

(including GBIF). We are particularly interested in non-GBIF data from EASIN (387,547 unique presence cells; March 2023).

- *Integrated European Long-Term Ecosystem, Critical Zone and socio-ecological Research (eLTER)*⁵¹: eLTER is a network of sites collecting ecological data for long-term research within the EU. We have obtained vegetation data for 137 eLTER sites, which come in different structures and formats. Our workflow homogenises these heterogeneous data into a single dataset, standardises plant taxonomy, and converts the data into HDF5 format to maintain the data in a binary state for efficient throughput rates.

Figure 16 – The log₁₀-transformed number of IAS per 10 km x 10 km (GBIF, EASIN, and eLTER)

Only observations made after 1980 were considered. For EASIN data, we only show data from data providers other than GBIF.

- **Habitat type:** We will use habitat data either directly as a predictor(s) or as a filter when preparing model predictions. We converted CORINE (Coordination of Information on the Environment) land cover data⁵²⁻⁵³, derived from Copernicus⁵⁴, into ecologically meaningful broad habitat types. CORINE land cover (CLC) classes are converted into the habitat classification of Pyšek et al. [6] using a custom crosswalk (based on our experience and knowledge from the literature). Original CLC data is available at the same projection of the EEA reference grid at 100 m resolution. From CLC data, we calculated the percentage coverage of each habitat type per grid cell as long as determining the most common habitat type per grid cell.
- **Climate data:** CHELSA⁵⁵ [7] provides global high-resolution (30 arc seconds; ~1 km) data on various environmental variables currently and in different future climate scenarios. Our workflow processes 46 potential climatological variables available under current and future climates into our reference grid. In addition to current climate conditions, there are 45 future scenarios we will consider (5 climate CMIP6 models × 3 shared socioeconomic pathways [ssp126 - ssp370 - ssp585] × 3 time slots [2011-2040 - 2041-2070 - 2071-2100]).
- **Sampling effort:** We computed the total number of vascular plant observations made after 1980 per grid cell in GBIF database (>229 million occurrences, March 2023). This variable is considered a proxy of the sampling effort for vascular plants across Europe and will be used to correct for spatial sampling bias in the opportunistic presence-only GBIF data.

⁵¹ <https://elter-ri.eu/>

⁵² <https://land.copernicus.eu/en/products/corine-land-cover>

⁵³ <https://doi.org/10.2909/960998c1-1870-4e82-8051-6485205ebbac>

⁵⁴ Earth observation component of the European Union’s Space programme; <https://www.copernicus.eu/>

⁵⁵ Climatologies at high resolution for the earth’s land surface areas; <https://chelsa-climate.org/>

- **Road density:** The Global Roads Inventory Project (GRIP⁵⁶) [8] dataset was used to prepare the road intensity map in Europe. Our workflow gets the most recent version of road maps, projects it into our reference grid, and calculates the total length (in km) of roads per grid cell. This variable represents site accessibility (i.e., describe spatial sampling bias in opportunistic GBIF data), the level of habitat disturbance, and the dispersal of IAS.
- **Railway density:** Our workflow downloads up-to-date global railway infrastructure data from OpenRailwayMap⁵⁷, projects it into our reference grid, and calculates the total length of railways (in km) per grid cell. This variable serves as a proxy for IAS dispersal routes.

Data Storage and Availability

Initially, IASDT will use LUMI's Object Storage (LUMI-O⁵⁸) for model input/output data at each workflow run. A clone of select data will be available via a data server built using an in-house OPeNDAP Catalog⁵⁹. Further technical solutions for data storage are in the process of being explored in BioDT, including as part of work carried out with regard to data streams.

LUMI-O gives a public web interface for each file in their "buckets". Some of our example data files are provided below.

- CSV: <https://465000357.lumidata.eu/iasdt-pub/bzf-catalogue-survey.csv>
- HDF5: <https://465000357.lumidata.eu/iasdt-pub/elter-vegetation.hdf5>
- NetCDF4: https://465000357.lumidata.eu/iasdt-pub/coads_climatology.nc
- RData⁶⁰: https://465000357.lumidata.eu/iasdt-pub/Grid_10_Raster.RData

A problem with using LUMI-O as an interim solution is that the entire files need to be downloaded to work within third-party systems. The OPeNDAP server will clone some defined data from LUMI-O into a Virtual Machine using Docker and will serve it using the Data Access Protocol (DAP), which is a defined data model⁶¹ for accessing remote scientific datasets. Using DAP enables users to query subsets of the data files, while automatically giving variable-level access⁶² and automatically assigning metadata to the contents of each file⁶³.

The IASDT will mainly work with CSV, HDF5, RData, JSON, and NetCDF file formats for data storage and availability.

Metadata

There are four types of metadata in the IASDT:

1. **Feedback-loop metadata:** JSON files that track changes in the data sources.
2. **State metadata:** JSON files that show the difference between consecutive input data from workflow run to workflow run (i.e., what has changed over time).
3. **Runtime metadata:** Log files for the workflow runs.
4. **Model metadata:** Log files of the model runs + JSON files based on template from Zurell et al. [9].

⁵⁶ <https://www.globio.info/download-grip-dataset>

⁵⁷ <https://www.openrailwaymap.org/>

⁵⁸ <https://docs.lumi-supercomputer.eu/storage/lumio/>

⁵⁹ https://git.ufz.de/khant/pydap_template

⁶⁰ A native binary format for saving multiple R objects in a single file.

⁶¹ https://www.opendap.org/pdf/dap_objects.pdf

⁶² e.g. http://134.94.199.14/nc/coads_climatology.nc.html

⁶³ e.g. http://134.94.199.14/nc/coads_climatology.nc.das

All the metadata within the IASDT will be created using RO-Crate guidelines⁶⁴.

2.3.1.1.3 Model

Repository (internal only; available over request by contacting on <https://biодt.eu/form/contact>):

- <https://git.ufz.de/biодt/IASDT-Modelling>: A git repository hosts R scripts for data preparation and model fitting. Scripts for data preparation are stored here only during the script development and will be moved to the workflow repository (see below) next year.
- <https://git.ufz.de/biодt/IASDT.R>: An R package for internal use by the IASDT. The package contains helper functions for data preparation and model fitting.

Programming languages & tooling: R, Bash, Git

Description:

We have almost finalised the species list for the models, the gridded distribution of species, and species-habitat type affinity. We will use JSDMs [10-11] to model multiple species together in a single framework that accounts for species co-occurrence patterns. More specifically, JSDMs model species simultaneously while accounting for species correlations that can be attributed to species interactions and missing covariates. Models will be fit using the Hmsc⁶⁵ R package⁶⁶ [12-13]. As it is expected to be computationally intensive to run a single model for hundreds of species across Europe, our current plan is to run a separate JSDM per habitat type. We plan to start working on modelling the distribution of IAS across Europe in November 2023. We are currently working on testing containerisation on LUMI. This Singularity container will help to manage an independent and self-contained R environment (including having control over the versions of R and its packages) for the model executions. We expect to have a prototype of models on a subset of species (for a single habitat type) run on LUMI by February 2024.

2.3.1.1.4 Pipeline scripts

Code Repository (internal only): <https://git.ufz.de/biодt/iasdt-workflows>
(Available over request by contacting on <https://biодt.eu/form/contact/>)

Programming languages: Python, R, Bash

Main tooling: [Git](#), [PyDolt](#), [Docker](#), [DVC](#)

Output file formats: NetCDF, JSON, CSV, HDF5, RData

Description: This GitLab project hosts the data pipeline scripts and configuration files for the IASDT Data Workflows. This project will be mirrored on the BioDT GitHub organisation⁶⁷ soon for open access, however it will remain of the UFZ Gitlab until initial development and testing is done. The pipeline is responsible for collecting, processing, and servicing input data from various sources, enabling the model to use the input data downstream. The data pipeline is built using the PyDolt automation tool, that generates execution Directed Acyclic Graphs⁶⁸ (DAGs) from defined "Tasks" and "Actions".

Repository Structure:

- **workflows/**

⁶⁴ <https://www.researchobject.org/ro-crate/>

⁶⁵ Hierarchical Model of Species Communities

⁶⁶ <https://www.helsinki.fi/en/researchgroups/statistical-ecology/software/hmsc>

⁶⁷ <https://github.com/BioDT>

⁶⁸ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Directed_acyclic_graph

<https://www.biодt.eu/>

- **feedbackloops/**: Python scripts for detecting changes in and extracting data from source systems.
- **process/**: Python and R scripts for transforming and cleaning the extracted data, handling data quality checks and aggregations. Also data assimilation scripts.
- **state/**: Python scripts that track and manage the state space of the IASDT. The state space is defined as the changes in the input data from one workflow run to the next.
- **service/**: Python scripts for loading the processed data into our data warehouse, which is hosted on LUMI-O.
- **dodo.py**: PyDoit configuration file containing parameters for the pipeline. Execution flow, Tasks and Actions are also defined in this script.
- **logs/**
 - **diff/**: contains logs on the state space of the IASDT. Carrying information on what is changing in the input data over time
 - **feedback/**: Log files of individual feedback loop runs
- **datasets/**
 - **raw/**: Raw downloaded files from the source. Only from the last workflow execution.
 - **interim/**: Temporary storage folder for files that are being prepared during the workflow runs.
 - **processed/**: The final processed files from the last workflow execution. This folder here will be cloned on LUMI-O and will have Data Version Control (DVC)⁶⁹ running to version datasets.
- **docs/**: Folder with documentation and data dictionaries to explain the structure and meaning of the data.
- **requirements.txt**: Python module dependencies.
- **renv.lock**: R module dependencies.
- **ro-crate-metadata.json**: Workflow metadata.
- **.env**: Environment variables used at runtime.

Continuous Integration/Continuous Deployment (CI/CD):

We have set up CI/CD pipelines in GitLab to automatically test and deploy changes to our data pipeline. All changes pushed to the **main** branch trigger automated tests and deployments.

Collaboration:

We encourage collaboration and contributions from the data engineering and analytics teams. Please create pull/merge requests for any enhancements or bug fixes.

2.3.1.1.5 Pilot study

Here is the current information on the pilots of the four components of IASDT as defined in the IASDT architecture.

1. Pilot workflow run on LUMI

A test workflow run of a subset of the pipeline (CHELSA climate data) is currently planned for November 2023. The aim is to test the following aspects of the workflow:

- Integration of Python and R on LUMI
- Storage performance of large datasets on LUMI-O
- Workflow performance
- Debugging and optimisation

⁶⁹ <https://dvc.org/>
<https://www.biodt.eu/>

2. Pilot OPeNDAP data server

A pilot instance of the OPeNDAP server is currently running on: <http://134.94.199.14/> at the Jülich Supercomputing Centre⁷⁰.

Code Repository (under development): <https://git.ufz.de/khant/opedap>

Documentation (under development):

<https://khant.pages.ufz.de/opedap/chapters/concept/opedap.html>

The following data storage formats are supported as DAP objects:

- HDF5
- CSV, with JSON metadata
- NetCDF4
- SQL

The server can also be used to download any other data format, like RData, Zarr, or Pickle. However, no DAP object support exists outside the abovementioned formats.

3. Pilot model run

We are currently working on testing containerisation on LUMI. We will start working on the modelling in November 2023. Our plan is to have a pilot model run for a subset of data on LUMI by February 2024.

4. Pilot dashboard

A pilot of the dashboard is currently planned for 2024.

2.3.1.1.6 Envisaged users

IASDT is intended at policy makers in the fields of natural resources and nature conservation, scientists, conservation managers, citizen science groups, and pest control authorities.

2.3.1.1.7 FAIR statement

We will reference GBIF species occurrence data using persistent identifiers. For environmental data sources, we will provide already existing identifiers. The state changes of the DT (input + output) will be tracked from execution to execution and stored, tracked and made available with persistent identifiers, which will add to the provenance of the DT. All data pre- and post-processing steps will be implemented using reproducible workflows and made publicly available. All the model, workflow code, and datasets will be described through metadata using RO-Crate and made publicly available. We will use versioning for all analyses.

2.3.1.1.8 References

1. Darema F (2004) Dynamic data driven applications systems: A new paradigm for application simulations and measurements. International conference on computational science. Berlin, Heidelberg: Springer Berlin Heidelberg.
2. Kapteyn MG, Willcox KE (2020) Predictive digital twins: Where dynamic data-driven learning meets physics-based modeling. Dynamic Data Driven Applications Systems: Third International Conference, DDDAS 2020, Boston, MA, USA, October 2-4, 2020, Proceedings 3. Springer International Publishing.
3. Gallagher J, Potter N, Sgouros T (2004). DAP data model specification DRAFT. Retrieved November, 6, 2004.
4. Cornillon P, Gallagher J, Sgouros T (2003). OPeNDAP: Accessing data in a distributed, heterogeneous environment. *Data Science Journal* 2: 164-174. <https://doi.org/10.2481/dsj.2.164>

⁷⁰ <https://www.fz-juelich.de/en/ias/jsc>
<https://www.biodt.eu/>

5. Chamberlain S, Barve V, Mcglinn D, et al. (2023). rgbif: Interface to the Global Biodiversity Information Facility API. R package version 3.7.8, <https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=rgbif>.
6. Pyšek P, Sádlo J, Chrtěk J Jr, et al. (2022) Catalogue of alien plants of the Czech Republic (3rd edition): species richness, status, distributions, habitats, regional invasion levels, introduction pathways and impacts. *Preslia* 94: 447–577, <https://doi.org/10.23855/preslia.2022.447>
7. Karger DN, Conrad O, Böhrer J, et al. (2017) Climatologies at high resolution for the Earth land surface areas. *Scientific Data*. 4 170122. <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2017.122>
8. Meijer JR, Huijbregts MAJ, Schotten CGJ, et al. (2018) Global patterns of current and future road infrastructure. *Environmental Research Letters*, 13-064006. Data is available at www.globio.info
9. Zurell D, Franklin J, König C, et al. (2020) A standard protocol for reporting species distribution models. *Ecography* 43(9):1261-77. DOI: 10.1111/ecog.04960.
10. Ovaskainen O, Abrego N (2020) Joint species distribution modelling: With applications in R. Cambridge University Press. ISBN: 9781108591720
11. Wilkinson DP, Golding N, Guillera-Arroita G, et al. (2021) Defining and evaluating predictions of joint species distribution models. *Methods in Ecology and Evolution* 12: 394–404. <https://doi.org/10.1111/2041-210X.13518>
12. Ovaskainen O, Tikhonov G, Norberg A, et al. (2017) How to make more out of community data? A conceptual framework and its implementation as models and software. *Ecology Letters* 20, 561-576. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ele.12757>
13. Tikhonov G, Opedal ØH, Abrego N, et al. (2020) Joint species distribution modelling with the R-package Hmsc. *Methods in ecology and evolution*; 11(3):442-7. <https://doi.org/10.1111/2041-210X.13345>

2.4 Species interactions with each other and with humans

2.4.1 Disease outbreaks

2.4.1.1 Wild boar–domestic pig wildlife disease modeling and pathogen spillover use case

2.4.1.1.1 Background of pDT

The purpose of this pDT is to inform data-driven responses to manage spread of wildlife diseases, specifically African swine fever (ASF). The model is intended to be dynamic: with each detection of the target pathogen in the wildlife population, the model is updated and rerun to produce more robust predictions including spatial mapping of risk, size, and timeline of affected host(s), effectiveness of spatially-explicit control measures, and routine update of most suitable response. The target audience for the initial pDT is restricted to decision makers and people involved in decision support.

Figure 17 – The Wild boar-African Swine Fever pDT in a nutshell

This BioDT pDT, conceptualised in Figure 17, aims to implement a stochastic, spatially-explicit wild boar (*Sus scrofa*)-ASF predictive model that is both dynamic and periodic on a structured landscape [1,2]. Given the input data for a specific study area (a habitat structural model, individual wild boar information, and barrier data) [1,2], the model returns a spatiotemporally dynamic prediction of ASF infection in the wild boar population at weekly time intervals. Users will have access to, and the ability to download, a standardised array of model outputs. Additionally, users should have the opportunity to provide additional data inputs, specifically spatiotemporal information about infected wild boar individuals and potential management/containment scenarios. Provision of these additional data will trigger the model to re-run under the influence of the new information.

2.4.1.1.2 Data

Users can provide both initial input and dynamic model data. These data, as well as the returned model predictions, will initially be saved in a project facilitated repository on LUMI.

- *Input data.* Model input data consist of a structural habitat model (source: [ENetWild](https://enetwild.com/), <https://enetwild.com/>, or user-provided). Landscape structure data (user created or obtained via ENetWild⁴¹) in the form of a numerical grid (ascii, GeoTiff, or other Python readable format) initiate the first iteration of the wild boar–ASF model. See this example [1] of ENetWild data that can be used in creating the initial model input data. The model includes a sub-module to ensure standardisation of these data into the correct format for integration into the model.
- *Dynamic data.* Dynamic data consist of barrier data (source: user-provided), wild boar geolocation information with infection status (source: user-provided). Users will be able to provide periodic data updates specifically related to (1) wild boar location and infection status and (2) potential virus control measures. To enable this, the project will require functionality to allow users to upload wild boar geolocation information (e.g., a text or comma delimited file with point coordinates and a short attribute list including status of ASF infection) as well as barrier data, typically as a shapefile, line elements consisting of barriers, lines, and segments that create barriers between cells including an accessible webform and LUMI object storage for both data types. While LUMI-O is used in the interim, further technical solutions for data storage are in the process of being explored in BioDT, including as part of work carried out with regard to data streams. Further, the model does not yet have a module to automate gridding of barrier data (this functionality will need to be added).

2.4.1.1.3 Model

Module overview. In its most basic form, the model is static and stochastic in that modeling (including 10,000 parallelised iterations) is initiated with ingestion of the structural habitat model and, after the model output is provided, modeling ceases. The model is intended to be run periodically with a dynamic data stream such that additional data are added by the user at prescribed intervals (e.g., weekly) automatically triggering the model to re-run with the new input data.

The core wild boar–ASF model [1,2] is written in Rust as an entity component system (ECS) such that all sub-modules have the same interface and structure [3]. A Python wrapper allows for custom configuration of the sub-modules [4]. The model is not computationally intensive and does not include interactions. However, should the wild boar–domestic swine ASF spillover model reach fruition, that is, if the coupling mechanism to bridge the two populations is developed and model links established, interactions will be necessary to account for the two-way coupling of two stochastic models. Currently, the LUMI CPU partition should be sufficient to run both the individual and potentially coupled models.

Module configuration. The model sub-module components include capability to standardise the habitat structure model and wild boar geolocation data. An automated workflow standardising gridding of barrier data will need to be developed. Although customisable, user-defined configuration of the modeling workflow will not be initially implemented. Instead, we will designate a default sub-module configuration for initial stages of UC development and implementation. Although customisable, initial model testing and implementation will use a default model structure. Functionality to adjust sub-module configuration may be considered for specific users further in development.

User interface. The user interface should provide controlled or restricted access such that individual users will have their own password protected account allowing for access to their archived inputs and model outputs in LUMI object storage. Interface functionality should include:

- Input data interface: The interface should include an accessible webform facilitating periodic upload and archiving of their own data. User provided data will come in two (2) forms:

- *Wild boar geolocation with infection status*: These data will be provided as text (.txt) or comma delimited files with point coordinates and a short attribute list including status of ASF infection.
- *Potential virus control measures (barrier data)*: Control data will typically be imported as a shapefile (.shp) consisting of lines elements and segments that create barriers between cells.
- **Model results**: The interface should allow users to view, archive, and download modeling results in a standardised format (format to be determined). Outputs should be downloadable in movie, gif, or similar format; static data should be available as PDF summary output and individual graphics (e.g., maps, graphs) should be downloadable individually in high-resolution. Model outputs will consist of three (3) primary components:
 - summaries of projected outcomes
 - static model graphics (maps, graphs, etc.) summarising projected outcomes
 - spatially dynamic views of model predictions through time
- **Archived data access**: Users should have the ability to access previously uploaded data as well as model outputs from all runs.

Spillover model. The framework for bridging the wildlife host-pathogen model to assess spillover risk in domestic swine populations is in the early stages of development and its inclusion in the pDT is, as yet, uncertain. The inclusion of such a model, though of great interest for the broader application of the pDT, would require a significant amount of time and effort dedicated to code and module development. It is presently unclear whether the necessary resources will be available to implement the model within the project timeline.

2.4.1.1.4 Pipeline scripts

Model components are modularised and well-documented [1—4]. Each module is written in Rust and encased in a Python wrapper. The initial BioDT UC will run the model using a default configuration (yet to be determined) that will be made available with project documentation.

Published code and documentation:

Rust: https://ecoepi.eu/ecoepi/supl/ODD-swifco-rs/rust/swifco_rs/index.html

Python wrappers: <https://ecoepi.eu/ecoepi/supl/ODD-swifco-rs/index.html>

Code repository - minimum working model (internal): Closed access (by invitation only) on the Helmholtz AAI

Code repository - official pDT model: BioDT GitHub

Repository structure - official pDT model: To be determined

Programming languages: Rust, Python

Input file formats: GeoTIFF, raster, JSON, shapefile, text, comma delimited

Output file formats: GIF, JPEG, PNG, PDF

2.4.1.1.5 Pilot study description and results

A pilot study to be conducted in a local environment is currently being developed. The specifics of this study have yet to be determined; however, the model exists in its entirety. It has been modularised. The model creators, Hans-Hermann Thulke (UFZ) and Martin Lange (UFZ), have made a fundamental working model and test data that are available for exploration. The study will include in-depth exploration of the code underlying each of the model sub-modules, identify any gaps or pressing needs in terms of code development, and

assess transferability and upscaling potential of the model to LUMI. Pilot study description/methodology and results will be made available when they are ready, and wireframe schematic will be updated accordingly.

2.4.1.1.6 Envisaged users

Although there are multiple potential stakeholders and user groups, the target audience for the initial BioDT application is limited to decision makers and people involved in decision support.

2.4.1.1.7 FAIR statement

Given the sensitive nature of disease modeling due to its direct relation to human health, much of the data associated with this UC will not be truly FAIR and open.

- *Initial model input data*: ENetWILD data are partially FAIR. Data can be accessed through the project website by project members, are citable, and are interoperable; but, at present, there is no direct API access to project data nor do the data have a globally persistent identifier. User-provided structural models may or may not be FAIR – this will be determined by the user.
- *User-provided dynamic data*: these data are not likely to be FAIR. Wild boar geolocation data may eventually become publicly available (e.g., via GBIF), but correlated information regarding infection status may remain closed access. This will depend on the original data source. Viral control measures, or barrier scenarios, are unlikely to ever become FAIR, particularly considering that barrier data provided users will likely be exploratory in that potential policy makers will explore a variety of barrier options to predict (evaluate) the efficacy of proposed control measure measures.
- *Model outputs*: All model outputs should be FAIR. However, in the current (prototype) implementation of this UC, it will be up to the user to determine the extent to which model outputs are open.

Model: The wild boar model itself is already published and documented [1–4]; the specific implementation (e.g., module configuration) to be used in the BioDT project will be made available with project documentation.

2.4.1.1.8 References

1. Lange M., Thulke H.H., 2017. Elucidating transmission parameters of African swine fever through wild boar carcasses by combining spatio-temporal notification data and agent-based modelling. SERR 31:379-391. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00477-016-1358-8>
2. Lange M., Thulke H.H., 2017. Elucidating transmission parameters of African swine fever through wild boar carcasses by combining spatio-temporal notification data and agent-based modelling Supplemental Material: ODD Model Documentation. SERR 31:379-391. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00477-016-1358-8>
3. ASF wild boar model Rust documentation: https://ecoepi.eu/ecoepi/supl/ODD-swifco-rs/rust/swifco_rs/
4. ASF wild boar model Python module documentation: <https://ecoepi.eu/ecoepi/supl/ODD-swifco-rs/index.html>

2.4.2 Pollinators

2.4.2.1 Honey bee dynamics in agricultural landscapes

2.4.2.1.1 Background of pollination pDT

Honey bees (*Apis mellifera*) provide important services by producing honey and pollinating commercial crops but also a wide range of wild flowers. Therefore, honey bees contribute to diversity but also rely to some extent on diverse landscapes, since bees depend on the continuous provision of nectar and pollen in particular in times when the mass flowering crops (e.g. oil seed rape) are not available. Honey bees face multiple stressors such as intensive agriculture, diseases and temporal limitation in nectar and pollen supply.

<https://www.biodt.eu/>

Digital twin applications can help to assess the quality of a given landscape for honey bee performance and honey production. This pDT is a first crucial step in terms of developing tools for other insect pollination species. Such a Digital Twin is presented in Figure 18. Freely accessible land use data, weather data and beekeeping regimes drive the open source simulation model BEEHAVE which can be calibrated by stock weight data. The user interface is implemented as an R Shiny app.

Figure 18 – Overview of the pollination/honeybee UC

Input data is already available and can be accessed any time. The simulation model is also ready to use and available for anyone anytime. The calibration/validation can be accessed by a web interface, but is not yet ready for automatic data request. All elements that are ready are in white and all elements that need further development are in black.

2.4.2.1.2 Data

Land cover data is based on a map by Preidl and colleagues [1]. The data is freely available from the Pangea server⁷¹. The data comes as raster data and has to be converted into polygons for our application. To do so we use the freely available statistical software R. Especially we use the R package terra to manipulate the land use data⁷². We request weather data by using an api provided through the R package rdwd⁷³. Daily sun shine hours and maximum daily temperatures of the nearest DWD weather station are requested and converted into daily foraging hours. The weather data is freely available. We learnt that there are data gaps in the DWD data. Thus, we are planning to replace the DWD data input by another product using the building block to download data from the Copernicus platform. Other input options such as bee keeping practices can be customized by the user. In addition to the input data it is planned to use monitoring data from the Trachtnet project where changes in the weight of beehives are recorded on a 5-minute resolution⁷⁴. This data will be used for calibration and testing. At the moment the data can be requested by anyone through a web interface. The access through this web interface is not feasible within this project, because it would require manual download. The host of the data⁷⁵ has provided us with the full data set. We are planning to develop a workflow to request subsets of this data. The automatic download procedure will be used internally in the beginning, but it is intended to make the data and data requesting available for everyone. Within the work package 6 and 4 there is a strong interest to use the same weather respectively climate data. Most likely Copernicus⁷⁶ data would be used.

⁷¹ <https://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.910837>. As requested on the 21th December 2022.

⁷² <https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/terra/index.html>. As requested on the 21th December 2022.

⁷³ <https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/rdwd/index.html>. As requested on the 21th December 2022.

⁷⁴ <https://www.bienenkunde.rlp.de>. As requested on the 21th December 2022

⁷⁵ Fachzentrum Bienen und Imkerei, Dienstleistungszentren ländlicher Raum. <https://www.bienenkunde.rlp.de>

⁷⁶ <https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/>. As requested on the 21th December 2022.

2.4.2.1.3 Model

The simulation model BEEHAVE [2], which has been implemented in NetLogo [3], has a rich set of potential output that can be stored at the end of a defined time period or at daily time steps. The simulation is usually run for one honey bee colony for 1 to 10 years in a circular landscape (represented by patches) with a typical radius of 1 to 10 km. Response variables that we will investigate in our study will be:

- Population viability of single honey bee colonies, quantified via winter mortality of the colonies.
- The abundances of all life stages (eggs, pupae, larvae, and adult bees), honey storage in the hive, pollen storage in the hive, flight activity, and the number of *Varroa* mites.

Additional information can be stored if necessary (see the manual of the BEEHAVE model at beehave-model.net for details). Currently the model BEEHAVE provides the results as csv files which can be downloaded by the user and individually analysed. Typical results would be time series of the number of bees, the amount of stored honey and the number of *Varroa* mites.

Pipeline scripts

The GUI for the user is implemented as an R Shiny application. Scripts have been developed to specify the input data (drivers) and to transform the input data into input files that can be read in to the BEEHAVE simulation model. Input of weather data will be through the `rdwd` R package. The simulation experiments will be specified and executed by a R script as well using the `nlr` package. The software required for executing the model (NetLogo, Java, R with `nlr` and other packages) have been bundled in a Docker container image that can be pulled and executed on LUMI through Apptainer / Singularity and on a cloud through Docker. The main performance bottleneck of the pDT is the large number of input data that requires processing. To overcome this, the execution of the containerised BEEHAVE model has been parallelised on the LUMI CPU partition (LUMI-C) over individual inputs by using HyperQueue:

<https://it4innovations.github.io/hyperqueue/stable>

This way the pDT can be executed in parallel on hundreds or thousands of cores, leveraging the large computing capacity of LUMI-C. The source code is hosted on the BioDT GitHub organisation (with access currently invitation-only, see Section 2.4.2.1.4 for further discussion).

The pDT can be applied to other countries, provided that data on land use, conversion of land use type into nectar and pollen resources, and weather data are available

2.4.2.1.4 Pilot study description and results

We have used the pDT to predict the number of surviving bees and honey storage using a regular grid spanning over 3000 locations in Germany, based on the surrounding land cover types and weather data. The bee number map shown in Figure 19 is based on simulations that have been run on LUMI. The results are preliminary and need further calibration and post processing. To make the pDT available to RIs, a R Shiny-based graphical user interface can be accessed via a floating address distributed internally to RIs involved in the project. The pDT is as of October 2023 not yet publicised to the broader public as it is in a prototype stage, with plans in place to begin presenting it to selected audiences outside of the consortium. A first general public release is planned in Q1 of 2024. The simulations of the pilot study need post processing.

Figure 19 – Test runs for the pollination pDT based on simulations that have been executed on LUMI

Purple clusters in the map are results of insufficient weather input data. The application needs further calibration and post processing, but as a proof of concept we can show that the pDT is functional.

The two planned pilot studies were postponed to 2024 (Sensitivity analysis and calibration) to allow for prioritisation of getting the pollination pDT running and to implement a GUI that can be also utilised by other pDTs.

2.4.2.1.5 Envisaged users

Researchers in academia, industry and bee institutes in the short term and interested bee keepers in the long term. In November 2023 we will invite researchers from industry, research and federal agencies (JKI Braunschweig) to test our pDT.

2.4.2.1.6 FAIR statement

The goal of BioDT is to make all components of the pDT as FAIR as possible, and not only the data (so including the model itself, the pipeline scripts, etc).

As mentioned, the BEEHAVE model, and most of the data and software packages are open and publicly available. For them and also those elements which are currently in development for the pDT, metadata descriptions are being developed. These are progressing well thanks to the existing and extensive documentation or metadata already available for the BEEHAVE model and its data sources. They will be added to the BioDT GitHub, either to the aforementioned BEEHAVE repositories, or to the specific repository for FAIR-related matters:

<https://github.com/BioDT/biodt-fair>

The metadata descriptions for BEEHAVE are being developed as RO-Crates, since it's the standard format used in BioDT. This also helps with aligning metadata descriptions with other pDTs.

Some of the FAIR principles can be achieved by packaging the pDT (and its subcomponents) as RO-Crates. Others, however, have to do with how the pDT and its outputs will be made available to the public (e.g. on

<https://www.biodt.eu/>

which open repositories to publish the data, etc) and similar matters, which are still ongoing discussions in BioDT.

2.4.2.1.7 References

1. Preidl, S., et al. (2020). Introducing APiC for regionalised land cover mapping on the national scale using Sentinel-2A imagery. *Remote Sensing of Environment* 240, 111673. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rse.2020.111673>
2. Becher, M. A., et al. (2014). BEEHAVE: a systems model of honeybee colony dynamics and foraging to explore multifactorial causes of colony failure. *Journal of Applied Ecology* 51(2): 470-482. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1365-2664.12222>
3. Wilensky, U. 1999. <http://ccl.northwestern.edu/netlogo/>. Center for Connected Learning and Computer-Based Modelling, Northwestern University. Evanston, IL.

3. Common data sources

Some of the pDTs use the same data sources as input for their models. This section provides an overview of the shared data sources for the different pDTs presented above.

3.1 Weather and climate data

Table 1 – Summary of weather and climate variables used and commonly shared within pDTs, their temporal and spatial resolution as well as data source

Variables	Temporal resolution	Spatial coverage	Shared data sources
Grassland Biodiversity & Pollinators			
(Max or mean) air temperature, rainfall & rainfall hours, global radiation or PAR, sunshine hours, PET	Daily	Resolution: local sites to km ² , <i>pDT Grassland Biodiversity</i> : Europe, <i>pDT Pollinators</i> : Germany	Copernicus ⁷⁷ , DWD ⁷⁸ (e.g. local weather stations), potentially DestinE
Invasive Species, Crop Wild Relatives & Cultural Ecosystem Services & Forest/bird Biodiversity			
Bioclimatic variables, Additionally, <i>pDT Invasive species</i> : PET (if available)	Long-term average (<i>pDT Forest/bird Biodiversity</i> : monthly)	Resolution: 100 m to 1 km ² , <i>pDT Ecosystem Services</i> : Scotland, <i>pDT Invasive species</i> : Europe, <i>pDT Crop wild relatives</i> : Tropical and subtropical part of the globe, <i>pDTs Forest/bird Biodiversity</i> : Finland	Earth System Grid Federation ⁷⁹ , CHELSA ⁸⁰ , WorldClim ⁸¹

⁷⁷ <https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu#!/home>

⁷⁸ https://www.dwd.de/DE/klimaumwelt/cdc/cdc_node.html

⁷⁹ <https://esgf-node.llnl.gov/projects/esgf-llnl/>

⁸⁰ <https://chelsa-climate.org/>

⁸¹ <http://www.worldclim.com/version2>

<https://www.biodt.eu/>

3.2 Land use data and land cover maps

Table 2 – Summary of land use data and land cover maps used and commonly shared within pDTs, their temporal and spatial resolution as well as data source

Variables	Temporal resolution	Spatial coverage	Shared data sources
Grassland Biodiversity, Pollinators, Invasive Species, Cultural Ecosystem Services & DNA detected biodiversity			
Land use / land cover habitat composition	Specific years, annual or average across years	Resolution: 20 m to 500 m (dependent on data source)	
		<i>pDT Grassland biodiversity</i> : Europe	Lange et al. 2021 ⁸² , Schwieder et al. 2022 ⁸³ , Preidl et al. 2020 ⁸⁴ , Pflugmacher et al. 2018 ⁸⁵
		<i>pDT Pollinators</i> : Germany	Preidl et al. 2020 ⁵⁷
		<i>pDT Invasive species</i> : Europe <i>pDT Forest/bird biodiversity</i> : Finland	Copernicus/CORINE ⁸⁶
		<i>pDT Cultural Ecosystem Services</i> : Scotland	Dynamic World V1 ⁸⁷ , UKCEH Land Cover Maps ⁸⁸
		<i>pDT DNA detected biodiversity</i> : Denmark	Levin, G. 2022 ⁸⁹
Invasive species			
Road density	Annual or average across years	shapefile	Global Roads Inventory Dataset (GLOBIO) ⁹⁰

⁸² <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S0034425722000025>

⁸³ <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0034425721005150>

⁸⁴ <https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.910837>

⁸⁵ <https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.896282>

⁸⁶ <https://land.copernicus.eu/pan-european/corine-land-cover>

⁸⁷ https://developers.google.com/earth-engine/datasets/catalog/GOOGLE_DYNAMICWORLD_V1

⁸⁸ <https://www.ceh.ac.uk/data/ukceh-land-cover-maps>

⁸⁹ <https://envs.au.dk/en/research-areas/society-environment-and-resources/land-use-and-gis/basemap/basemap04-geotiff-for-download>

⁹⁰ <https://www.globio.info/download-grip-dataset>

<https://www.biodt.eu/>

3.3 Soil data

Table 3 – Summary of soil variables used and commonly shared within pDTs, their temporal and spatial resolution as well as data source

Variables	Temporal resolution	Spatial coverage	Shared data sources
Grassland Biodiversity, Forest/bird biodiversity, Invasive Species, Cultural Ecosystem Services & Crop Wild Relatives			
Soil type / particle size distribution	None	Resolution: sample to 1 km ² (dependent on data source)	
		<i>pDTs Grassland Biodiversity, Invasive species: Europe, pDT Crop wild relatives: Tropical and subtropical parts of the globe</i>	SoilGrids250m ⁹¹
		<i>pDT Forest/bird biodiversity: Finland</i>	European Soil Data Centre/Soil Map ⁹²
Grassland Biodiversity			
Field capacity, permanent wilting point, porosity, hydraulic conductivity	None	Europe	HiHydroSoil map ⁹³
Invasive species & Cultural Ecosystem Services			
Bedrock, pH	None	<i>pDT Invasive species: Europe</i>	SoilGrids250m ⁹⁴

⁹¹ <https://soil-modeling.org/resources-links/data-portal/soilgrids250m>, <https://soilgrids.org/>

⁹² <http://esdac.jrc.ec.europa.eu/>

⁹³ <https://www.futurewater.eu/projects/hihydrosoil>

⁹⁴ <https://soil-modeling.org/resources-links/data-portal/soilgrids250m>

		<i>pDT Cultural Ecosystem Services: Scotland</i>	OpenLandMap Soil Organic Carbon Content ⁹⁵ , OpenLandMap Soil pH in H2O ⁹⁶
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3.4 Observation data

Table 4 – Summary of observation data used and commonly shared within pDTs, their temporal and spatial resolution as well as data source

Variables	Temporal resolution	Spatial coverage	Shared data sources
Grassland Biodiversity, Forest/bird Biodiversity, Cultural Ecosystem Services, Crop Wild Relatives, DNA Detected Biodiversity & Invasive Species, & Pollinators			
Leaf area index, species composition	All available data	<i>pDT Grassland Biodiversity: Europe</i>	Copernicus ERA5-Land dataset ⁹⁷ , eLTER grassland sites ⁹⁸
Species occurrences, <i>pDT Crop wild relatives: additional crop trait observations</i>	Yearly	<i>pDT Forest/bird biodiversity: Finland</i>	Finnish Museum of Natural History (LUOMUS) ⁹⁹
	Not aggregated	<i>pDT Cultural Ecosystem Services: Scotland</i>	GBIF ¹⁰⁰ , eLTER ⁷¹
	Not applicable	<i>pDT Crop wild relatives: Tropical and subtropical parts of the globe</i>	EURISCO ¹⁰¹ , GeneSys ¹⁰² , GBIF ⁷³ , ICARDA ¹⁰³ , crop trust ¹⁰⁴
	All available data (within geographical and taxonomic scope)	<i>pDT DNA detected biodiversity: Denmark</i>	GBIF API description ¹⁰⁵

⁹⁵ https://developers.google.com/earth-engine/datasets/catalog/OpenLandMap_SOL_SOL_ORGANIC-CARBON_USDA-6A1C_M_v02

⁹⁶ https://developers.google.com/earth-engine/datasets/catalog/OpenLandMap_SOL_SOL_PH-H2O_USDA-4C1A2A_M_v02

⁹⁷ <https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/cdsapp#!/dataset/reanalysis-era5-land?tab=overview>

⁹⁸ <https://elter-ri.eu/>

⁹⁹ <https://www.luomus.fi/en>

¹⁰⁰ <https://www.gbif.org/>

¹⁰¹ https://eurisco.ipk-gatersleben.de/apex/eurisco_ws/r/eurisco/home

¹⁰² <https://www.genesys-pgr.org/>

¹⁰³ <https://www.icarda.org/>

¹⁰⁴ <https://www.croptrust.org/deutsch/>

¹⁰⁵ <https://www.gbif.org/developer/summary>

	Aggregated across all years	<i>pDT Invasive species:</i> Europe	GBIF ⁷³ , EASIN ¹⁰⁶ , eLTER ⁷¹
Weight of beehives as proxy for hives (kg)	Daily	<i>pDT Pollinators:</i> Germany	Dienstleistungszentren Ländlicher Raum ¹⁰⁷

¹⁰⁶ <https://easin.jrc.ec.europa.eu/>

¹⁰⁷ <https://www.dlr.rlp.de>
<https://www.biodt.eu/>

4. Building blocks

Components and pipeline scripts of pDTs have been developed at two different levels:

- **Generic:** a component/script that can be used by DTs within BioDT as well as for a wider scientific community outside of BioDT (potentially for multiple purposes)
- **Specific:** a component/script that is developed with a single pDT in mind within BioDT

The degree to which components and scripts of one developed pDT can be used by another, multiple or even a wider range of DTs (either within or outside BioDT) defines the above-mentioned level. Components thereby include the various steps presented in the workflow schemes of the UCs (cf. sections above), but can also include steps within an illustrated component in the workflow schemes (i.e. small atomic scripts that can be reused easily). These can be, for example, certain steps and calculations in the input data processing or configurators (e.g. retrieving or processing of climate variables such as air temperature) and are closely linked to overlaps in common data sources (cf. section above).

For climatic and weather data such components have been developed generically (e.g. data stream of Copernicus / DWD weather variables for pDTs Grassland Biodiversity and Pollination). Land cover and land use data products as well as soil maps are available at different spatial and temporal resolutions for different regions or countries, and used by several pDTs, however, components of streaming and processing such data are specific as pDTs require different land use and soil variables for different regions.

Despite the share of pre-processed input data among pDTs (i.e. similar variables or data sources) which support generically used pipeline tools, the preparation of processed data to model-specific file formats is rather specific (especially, when mechanistic models are used only in one specific pDT like Grassland Biodiversity, Disease Outbreaks or Pollinators).

Components with respect to end-user interfaces and interactions are generic, i.e. in terms technical functionalities and implementation of interfaces (e.g. GUI or R Shiny application). pDT / model-specific components like output aggregations / summaries and model calibration / validation / evaluation as well as visualisations of model simulations are highly pDT-dependent, specifically, on the model type and its complexity (mechanistic vs. statistical approach) as well as on the observational data used. Thus, these components are pDT-specific (e.g. pDTs Grassland Biodiversity and Pollinators are based on mechanistic models and specific observation data, cf. 2.4).

Below, we summarise which components and scripts have been packaged as (i) generic and (ii) specific building blocks.

4.1 Generic building blocks

4.1.1 OPeNDAP Catalog

4.1.1.1 Description

Open-source Project for a Network Data Access Protocol (OPeNDAP) is a framework for remote scientific data networking and management. The framework is based on the Data Access Protocol (DAP), which is a data transmission protocol designed specifically for science data and has a defined data model¹⁰⁸. The protocol relies on the widely used and stable Hypertext Transfer Protocol (HTTP) and Multipurpose Internet Mail Extensions (MIME) standards, and provides data types to accommodate gridded data, relational data, and time series, as well as allowing users to define their own data types.

¹⁰⁸ https://www.opendap.org/pdf/dap_objects.pdf

The OPeNDAP Catalog is a software written in the BioDT project (specifically in the IASDT) that enables users to set up containerised (Docker) data servers for allowing remote access to scientific datasets as objects. It extends the existing open-source PyDAP¹⁰⁹ project with added functionality like linking to S3 storage systems, user management, improved handling of existing data formats and adding handlers for new data formats.

The software is containerised using Docker so it can be easily set up on any platform, and uses RClone to sync with many types of Object Storage systems (i.e. to clone and serve files in buckets). The software wraps PyDAP with Flask, NGINX and uWSGI to serve files and communicate with clients.

A pilot instance of OPeNDAP server is currently running at the Jülich Supercomputing Centre.

The following data storage formats are supported as DAP objects:

- HDF5
- CSV, with JSON metadata
- NetCDF4
- SQL

The server can also be used to download any other data format, like RData, Zarr, or Pickle.

Live version: <http://134.94.199.14/>

Repository: <https://git.ufz.de/khant/opensdap>

Documentation: <https://khant.pages.ufz.de/opensdap/chapters/concept/opensdap.html>

4.1.1.2 Application examples

The server can be used by any pDT in BioDT that wants to serve datasets/models remotely. Below are two examples.

4.1.1.2.1 As an interface for IASDT datasets on LUMI-O

The Invasive Alien Species Digital Twin initially aims to incrementally store its input/output data and models on buckets in LUMI-O. LUMI-O gives a public web interface for each individual file in their "buckets". Sample data files for certain file formats can be found in Section 2.3.1.1.

4.1.1.2.2 As a Data Catalog for the Community Ecology department at Helmholtz-UFZ

The OPeNDAP Catalog can also serve as a medium to long-term centralised data cataloging software. The Community Ecology department of the Helmholtz-UFZ is currently planning such a catalog using the OPeNDAP Catalog software.

4.1.2 Script for obtaining site-specific weather data from Copernicus

4.1.2.1 Description

For certain pDTs, daily time series of specific weather data over a simulation time period are needed as input data (cf. 3.1). The developed generic pipeline script (in Python) allows for specifying spatial locations, time periods, and the set of desired weather variables to be downloaded via the CDS API.

The building block is shared on the BioDT GitHub repository among pDT developers and invited test users, where it is also finalised and prepared for publication. Public availability is planned at the latest until May 2024 (Deliverable D6.2).

¹⁰⁹ PyDAP: <https://pydap.github.io/pydap/index.html>
<https://www.biodt.eu/>

4.1.2.2 Application example

This building block will be used by the pDTs on grassland biodiversity dynamics and pollinator survival. Figure 20 shows an example comparison of an air temperature time series retrieved via this generic pipeline compared to the reference time series retrieved from local measurements at a pilot study site (cf. 2.1.1.1). While the correspondence is not always as good as for this example, the automatically obtained weather data generally match the local reference data reasonably well. Moreover, deviations may also be due to non-optimal quality of the reference data.

Figure 20 – Air temperature (in °C) time series throughout 2014 for the grassland pilot study site

GCEF (Latitude 51.3919, Longitude 11.8787) from local measurements (blue) and the ERA5-Land dataset retrieved via the CDS API (red). Top plots show the direct comparison of single values (left, incl. identity line) and a histogram of deviations (right).

4.1.3 Script for obtaining land cover type from remote sensing maps

4.1.3.1 Description

This building block (cf. 3.1) can be used by several pDTs. For a given location or list of locations (provided as spatial coordinates latitude and longitude), the generic pipeline script (in Python) returns the land cover type(s) according to publicly available maps [e.g. 1, 2]. Further land cover maps will be included¹¹⁰.

The building block is shared on the BioDT GitHub repository among pDT developers and invited test users, where it is also finalised and prepared for publication. Public availability is planned at the latest until May 2024 (Deliverable D6.2).

¹¹⁰ e.g. Grassland 2018 (raster 10 m), Europe, 3-yearly, 2020. EEA Geospatial Data Cat.

<https://sdi.eea.europa.eu/catalogue/copernicus/api/records/60639d5b-9164-4135-ae93-fb4132bb6d83>; ESA

WorldCover 10 m 2021 v200. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7254220>

<https://www.biodt.eu/>

4.1.3.2 Application example

For the pDT on grassland biodiversity dynamics, the building block will be used to check whether a given candidate location for grassland simulations is actually classified as 'grassland' according to the selected land cover map (cf. 2.1.1.1). For the pDT on pollinator survival, it will be used for obtaining the landscape composition and calculating areas with flowering crops (e.g. oil seed rape) available to pollinators.

4.1.4 Script for obtaining soil data from SoilGrids250m map

4.1.4.1 Description

This building block (cf. 3.1) will allow obtaining soil data from the publicly available soil maps SoilGrids250m [3]. For a given location or list of locations (provided as spatial coordinates latitude and longitude), generic pipeline scripts (in Python) can either return the soil composition (silt/clay/sand proportions) directly from the SoilGrids250m map, or selected soil hydraulic properties from the HiHydroSoil map [4], which is based on the SoilGrids250m map and pedotransfer functions.

The building block is shared on the BioDT GitHub repository among pDT developers and invited test users, where it is also finalised and prepared for publication. Public availability is planned at the latest until May 2024 (Deliverable D6.2).

4.1.4.2 Application example

For the pDT “Grassland biodiversity dynamics”, the building block will be used to prepare the soil input data required for grassland simulations at a given location. This comprises both the soil composition, and a set of soil hydraulic properties (in vertical layers, cf. 2.1.1.1).

4.1.5 DEIMS package

4.1.5.1 Description

The publicly available Python package 'deims'¹¹¹ (developed by BioDT contributors Will Bolton and Christoph Wohner) provides an interface to the Dynamic Ecological Information Management System - Site and dataset registry (DEIMS-SDR)¹¹², which is the standard information management system for eLTER.

4.1.5.2 Application example

For BioDT applications, a specific function was added to the latest release of the package (deims 4.0), which allows directly retrieving the spatial coordinates of sites based on their DEIMS.iDs. For the pDT “Grassland biodiversity dynamics”, the building block will be used to obtain the spatial coordinates of an eLTER site, for which grassland data have been provided, further input data need to be prepared (using the spatial coordinates) and grassland simulation shall be executed (cf. 2.1.1.1).

4.2 Specific building blocks

Pipeline scripts specific to the pDTs that have been developed for the UCs are described in detail under Section 2 and the pDT-specific subsections (including information on the dissemination and respective links and access information).

¹¹¹ <https://pypi.org/project/deims/>

¹¹² <https://deims.org/>
<https://www.biodt.eu/>

References

1. Preidl S, Lange M, Doktor D (2020) Land cover classification map of Germany's agricultural area based on Sentinel-2A data from 2016. PANGAEA. <https://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.910837>
2. Pflugmacher D, Rabe A, Peters M, Hostert P (2018) Pan-European land cover map of 2015 based on Landsat and LUCAS data. PANGAEA. <https://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.896282>
3. Hengl T, Jesus JM de, Heuvelink GBM, et al (2017) SoilGrids250m: Global gridded soil information based on machine learning. *PLOS ONE* 12:e0169748. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0169748>
4. Simons, G, Koster R, Droogers P, 2020. HiHydroSoil v2.0 - A high resolution soil map of global hydraulic properties. FutureWater report 134, Wageningen, The Netherlands.

5. Conclusions and future work

5.1 Conclusions

pDT development was largely determined by how well developed and established the models to be used were from the start of the project. Hence, also the development of pipeline scripts is most advanced for pDTs where models existed (e.g. pDTs focusing on biodiversity dynamics or invasive species). Other pDTs have conceptualised their pipelines but not yet developed corresponding scripts, which was to be expected.

Ideally, the development of DTs for different aspects of biodiversity and addressing different management of policy questions would not always start from scratch but build on building blocks developed with existing DTs. While there are limits to using building blocks, it was possible to identify several candidate building blocks. Some of them are generic, like the OPeNDAP Catalog, but others are more specific but still applicable in a certain domain, while most building blocks have a much narrower focus. Still, the idea of building blocks is *not* to serve as plug and play components because their use will always, even in the most generic case, be context-dependent. Still, even the most specific building blocks provide a repository of solutions that can be adapted by others and thereby make pDT development more coherent and efficient. The same holds for another output described in this deliverable, i.e. the scripts for accessing common data sources. Further generic building blocks might be developed, potentially starting from specific building blocks, if synergies are found during the project.

Overall, progress on pipeline development, validation and release has been on schedule and forms the basis of the release of the pDTs developed in BioDT.

5.2 Future work

For the pDTs that have pipeline scripts, the next steps will focus on model validation and improving the predictive performance of models included in the pipelines, on further testing and refining the scripts, on making them more robust and permanent as well as on developing user interfaces and required functionalities. For the pDTs that, in parallel to the preparation of data and workflows, still require work on finalising the model development, the next task is pipeline script development. For this task, pDT contributors can benefit from the pipeline development in the other pDTs. A very important future work for all pDTs is the involvement of end users by letting them try and use the pDTs for their own questions and data. Two corresponding workshops are scheduled for November 2023 and January 2024.